

Istanbul
Bilgi University

LAUREATE INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITIES

European Institute

2018-19 **11**

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Ayhan Kaya

Director, European Institute
Department of International Relations
Istanbul Bilgi University

Yeşim M. Atamer

Vice-Director, European Institute
Faculty of Law
Istanbul Bilgi University

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Istanbul Bilgi University
European Institute

Tel: +90 212 311 52 60
Web: eu.bilgi.edu.tr
E-mail: europe@bilgi.edu.tr

Editor: Aslı Aydın-Sancar,
Dr. Ayşe Tecmen

JEAN MONNET CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE

BİLGİ EUROPEAN INSTITUTE NEWSLETTER

Dear Friends,

We would like to welcome you all to the 11th newsletter of the European Institute of İstanbul Bilgi University. This issue contains information on the Institute's activities, publications, conferences, workshops, graduate programs, research, social outreach projects and opinions of our staff and intern.

The newsletter starts with the depiction of our ongoing projects and activities carried out in 2018 by the European Institute, Assoc. Prof. Dr. Senem Aydın-Düzgüt (our partner from Sabanci University in Horizon 2020 FEUTURE project), Dr. Meltem Sancak (TUBITAK Fellow), and Dr. Özge Onursal-Beşgül and Dr. Mehmet Ali Tuğtan from the Department of International Relations. The first part also includes an interview with Gülperi Vural (former Project Manager of the European Institute) as well as news from our students, conferences and meetings.

This newsletter is designated as a special edition as we are in the final stages of the Horizon 2020 project titled "Critical Heritages: performing and representing identities in Europe" (CoHERE). To share our research findings and important innovative developments, the second part of this newsletter will focus on the CoHERE project, which investigates the significance of heritage and representations in Europe. In the CoHERE framework, we will illustrate how populist political movements have gained momentum across Europe based on our research. We will discuss the significance of culture, tolerance and diversity in Europe and in Turkey. Following these opinion pieces from our staff and guest writers, we will discuss the rising significance of digital education in social sciences drawing on the e-book for secondary school students that was produced as a part of the CoHERE project. This will also demonstrate how culture and heritage can be represented in a digital era.

On this occasion we would like to express our appreciation to the Rectorate and the Board of Trustees of İstanbul Bilgi University for their constant endorsement of the Institute. But most importantly, we would like to express our gratefulness to you all for your interest in the European Institute. We wish you all a pleasant New Year...

Prof. Ayhan Kaya
Director, European Institute

Prof. Yeşim M. Atamer
Vice-Director,
European Institute

CoHERE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 693289.

EUROPEAN RESEARCH COUNCIL (ERC)

“Nativism, Islamophobia And Islamism In The Age Of Populism: Culturalisation And Religionisation Of What Is Social, Economic And Political In Europe”

From: 01 January 2019 – To: 31 December 2023

Prof. Ayhan Kaya, faculty member of our university’s International Relations Department and Director of the European Union Institute has been awarded an “Advanced Grant” by the European Research Council (ERC), one of the most prestigious research institutions of Europe, for his project entitled “Nativism, Islamophobia and Islamism in the Age of Populism: Culturalisation and Religionisation of what is Social, Economic and Political in Europe”. For the purpose of more fairly evaluating research work at different levels, ERC offers three types of grants: A “Starting Grant” for young researchers, a “Consolidator Grant” for experienced researchers, and an “Advanced Grant” for scientists who perform high-level research at a global level. Prof. Ayhan Kaya’s project is the first social sciences project at a Turkish university to receive an “Advanced Grant” from ERC.

Prof. Kaya’s Research Summary:

The main research question of the study is: How and why do some European citizens generate a populist and Islamophobic discourse to express their discontent with the current social, economic and political state of their national and European contexts, while some members of migrant-origin communities with Muslim background generate an essentialist and radical form of Islamist discourse within the same societies? The main premise of this study is that various segments of the European public (radicalizing young members of both native populations and migrant-origin populations with Muslim background), who have been alienated and swept away by the flows of globalization such as deindustrialization, mobility, migration, tourism, social-economic inequalities, international trade,

and robotic production, are more inclined to respectively adopt two mainstream political discourses: Islamophobia (for native populations) and Islamism (for Muslim-migrant-origin populations). Both discourses have become pivotal along with the rise of the civilizational rhetoric since the early 1990s. On the one hand, the neo-liberal age seems to be leading to the nativisation of radicalism among some groups of host populations while, on the other hand, it is leading to the islamization of radicalism among some segments of deprived migrant-origin populations. The common denominator of these groups is that they are both downwardly mobile and inclined towards radicalization. Hence, this project aims to scrutinize social, economic, political and psychological sources of the processes of radicalization among native European youth and Muslim-origin youth with migration background, who are both inclined to express their discontent through ethnicity, culture, religion, heritage, homogeneity, authenticity, past, gender and patriarchy. The field research will comprise four migrant receiving countries: Germany, France, Belgium, and the Netherlands, and two migrant sending countries: Turkey and Morocco.

For further information of the European Research Council: <https://erc.europa.eu/>

HORIZON 2020 PROJECTS

Horizon 2020 Future of EU-Turkey Relations (FEUTURE)

THE FUTURE OF EU-TURKEY RELATIONS: MAPPING DYNAMICS AND TESTING SCENARIOS

www.feuture.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 692976.

From 01 April 2016 - To: 31 March 2019

FEUTURE (Future of EU-Turkey Relations) **reveals the narratives and drivers of the EU-Turkey relationship, the likely scenario(s) for the future, and the implications these may have on the EU and Turkey, as well as the neighbourhood and the global scene.** In forward-looking terms, FEUTURE contributes to the knowledge base of the external environment the EU operates in, providing a strong, evidence-based foundation from which the future trajectory of EU-Turkey relations may be drawn.

The project identifies six prevalent thematic dimensions of EU-Turkey relations that structure our research across four

levels of analysis: the EU, Turkey, the neighbourhood and the global scene.

The political dimension is most closely related with the overall pace of EU-Turkey relations. Research takes into consideration that progress in Turkey’s political performance has often been related to and has justified progress in Turkey’s European integration and vice versa. At the same time, setbacks in Turkey’s democratization has been linked to stagnation in its European integration path.

The economics dimension focuses on the economic ties between Turkey and the EU and the way these are conditioned both by the economic performances of the two sides and by relations with the neighbourhood and global markets. Security dimension:

In the security dimension, Turkey’s membership of NATO (as the second largest armed force in the Alliance) critically shapes EU-Turkey relations (as well as EU-NATO relations). Likewise, Turkish ambitions to become an independent regional power affect security ties with the EU. At the same time, Turkey’s relations with the EU condition both the EU and Turkey’s relations with the neighbourhood as well as with key global actors such as Russia and the United States.

In the light of Turkey’s growing importance for the EU’s quest for energy security through the diversification of energy sources and routes, **the energy dimension** will focus on whether Turkey will end up representing an energy hub, for Europe at the heart of the Southern Corridor and thus contribute to the EU’s energy security.

Concerning **the migration dimension**, the research analyses the flows of skilled migrants between Turkey and the EU, the transit of irregular migrants from Turkey into the EU, and the evolution of Turkish and EU asylum policies, and the way these have affected the broader scope of the EU-Turkey relationship. **The identity dimension** focuses on the diverse perception of identity of both Turkey and Europe by Turkish and EU actors.

The consortium includes 15 partner institutions including IAI in Italy; University of Cologne in Germany (coordinator); CIDOB in Spain; ELIAMEP in Greece; Middle East Technical University (METU), Centre for Economics and Foreign Policy Studies (EDAM), Koç University, İstanbul Bilgi University European Institute and Sabancı University from Turkey; Trans European Policy Studies Association (TEPSA), DIIS in Denmark; The American University in Cairo in Egypt, CIFE in France, Caucasus Resource Center CRRC in Georgia and MERI from Erbil, Northern Iraq.

Istanbul Bilgi University’s main tasks within FEUTURE

Contribution to:

WP1 “Conceptual and Analytical Toolkit”:

WP 1 which aims at providing an analytical toolkit for the project encompassing two steps: (1) historical analysis in light of narratives which have shaped the debate and political action both in Turkey and in the EU, thereby informing the scenario-building and the thematic analysis in WP 2-7; (2) conceptualising three forward-looking ideal-type scenarios for EU-Turkey relations: conflict, cooperation and convergence. The purpose of the scenario-building is to stylise what conditions would need to be met in the EU and in Turkey, and what would be the facilitating or constraining conditional factors at the neighbourhood and global levels, for the realisation of these scenarios.

WP6 “Migration Drivers”:

WP6 aims at identifying key direct and indirect migration-related drivers since 1999 at four levels of analysis (Turkey,

EU, neighbourhood, global) that are likely to lead to the realisation of one of the three envisaged ideal-type scenarios: conflict, cooperation or convergence in EU-Turkey relations. The WP analyses three focal issues: skilled migration, irregular (transit) migration, and asylum, since these three areas are currently the focus in the development of the European Agenda on Migration but also of importance to Turkey. Two main questions will be addressed: (1) What migration drivers are relevant and what constellation of them exist? (2) What are the most prominent drivers both within each focal issue and across them? Lastly, on the basis of the research results, the WP will be able to offer a projected most likely scenario regarding the future EU-Turkey relation in the area of migration.

WP8 “Synthesis of Research Findings and Policy Recommendations”:

WP 8 “Synthesis of Research Findings and Policy Recommendations” which has a threefold goal: (1) rank the drivers across the thematic WPs and synthesise the likely scenario across all thematic dimensions (2) assess the consequences of the three ideal type scenarios, and in particular of the empirically most likely scenario of EU-Turkey relations for the EU, Turkey, as well as for their relations with the neighbourhood (including on protracted regional conflicts, migratory patterns, trade and investment flows, energy dynamics and identity politics) and with global powers (US, Russia and emerging countries); (3) extrapolate evidence-based policy recommendations for the EU and for Turkey aimed at preventing a plausible worst-case scenario and realising a plausible best-case scenario for the EU-Turkey relationship, with an eye to the strategic interests of both parties.

WP9 “Dissemination and Outreach”:

WP 9 whose primary objective is to raise the awareness and knowledge about the drivers and implications of future scenarios of EU-Turkey relations as developed in WP1 to 8 and disseminate the findings of the project.

Review of WP 7 Findings:

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Senem Aydın Düzgit from Sabancı University and Bahar Rumelili, Ph. D. from Koç University who are the Resarcher involved in WP 7 Identity & Culture Drivers* wrote a paper on the progress of this Working Package.

FEUTURE Work Package on Culture and Identity (WP 7)

Senem Aydın-Düzgit

Bahar Rumelili

Senem Aydın-Düzgit and Bahar Rumelili

Against the background of the often polarised discussions both in the EU and Turkey on identity matters, this dimension is a fundamental element for substantiating future trajectories of EU-Turkey relations. Accordingly, this WP aims at identifying key drivers both in the EU and

Turkey as well as from a regional and global perspective that are likely to lead to the realisation of one of the three envisaged ideal-type scenarios – conflict, cooperation or convergence – in the EU-Turkey relationship. Taking into account the long-term view necessary for understanding identity constructions and cultural contexts, this WP adopts an encompassing approach, starting its analysis in the late Ottoman modernisation period, identifying key texts that are representative of dominant identity constructions in order to delineate the drivers. Two main questions are being addressed: (1) What identity and culture drivers are relevant and what constellations of them exist? (2) What are the most prominent drivers both within each focal issue and across them? As a last task, the weighing and ranking of the identified drivers aims at substantiating one or more of the proposed scenario(s) from an identity/culture perspective.

This WP begins with the analysis of Turkish and European identity constructions and their drivers in the late Ottoman modernization and early Republican period and follows with the analysis of mutual identity constructions in the Cold-War and the immediate post-Cold War period. The analysis of this period focuses on four focal issues which have played a critical role in shaping identity/cultural representations in different periods both in Europe and in Turkey, such as civilisation, state-citizen relations, nationalism and status in international society.

This WP also identifies the key drivers of identity and culture since 1999, through a study of the focal issues of religion, nationalism and secularism. In doing that, it traces the development of Turkey's role in politically hegemonic discourses within the European context as well as the concomitant rise to political hegemony of a nationalist discourse in this respect. Further, this task aims to map the main characteristics from the politics of secularism in Turkey-EU relations (invoking national government dynamics such as the resurgence of religion) and identify the drivers underpinning this particular area. Finally, this WP also traces identity representations of Turkey and Europe in regional (Egyptian and Georgian) and global (Russian and American) media since 1999.

The primary methodology which is employed in the analysis of the texts is Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), in particular the discourse-historical strand advocated mainly by the Vienna school. CDA is a method that focuses on the study of relations between discourse and social and cultural developments in different social domains. The research focuses on various genres such as leadership speeches, newspapers, and travel writings, since articulations of identity and culture can take different forms in different genres – situating these sources in the broader context.

The publications of the WP can be accessed at <http://www.feuture.eu/>.

* WP 7 Identity & Culture Drivers

This Work Package aims to identify historical and present drivers of EU-Turkey relations from an identity and culture perspective. Taking into account the long-term view necessary for understanding identity constructions and cultural contexts, this WP adopts an encompassing approach and starts its analysis in the late Ottoman modernisation period.

As a historical driver, it understands significant historical milestones that have influenced the EU-Turkey relationship and have shaped the mutual identity perceptions and representations. The analysis of present drivers focuses on national and supranational debates in Turkey and the EU, and on developments in Turkey-EU relations, with specific

emphasis on the rise of nationalism and debates around secularism.

Overall, the WP focuses on Turkey's and Europe's perceptions of each other in identity and cultural terms, which play a pivotal role in shaping the relationship. By identifying historical and contemporary patterns in the evolution of mutual identity perceptions, this work package aims to assess the likelihood of the three ideal type scenarios – conflict, cooperation, and convergence – materialising in the near future of EU-Turkey relations.

Two main questions will be addressed:

(1) What identity and culture drivers are relevant and what constellations of them exist?

(2) What are the most prominent drivers both within each focal issue and across them?

(3) As a last task, the weighing and ranking of the identified drivers will aim at substantiating one or more of the proposed scenario(s) from an identity/culture perspective.

Twitter: @FEUTURE_EU

Facebook: @feuture.eu

Horizon 2020 RESPOND: Multilevel Governance of Mass Migration in Europe and Beyond

"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 770564"

From: 01 December 2017 – To: 30 November 2020

With the goal of enhancing the governance capacity and policy coherence of the EU, its member states and neighbors, RESPOND is a comprehensive study of migration governance in the wake of the 2015 Refugee Crisis. Bringing together 14 partners from 7 disciplines, the project probes policy-making processes and policy (in) coherence through comparative research in source, transit and destination countries. RESPOND analyzes migration governance across macro (transnational, national), meso (sub-national/local) and microlevels (refugees/migrants) by applying an innovative research methodology utilizing legal and policy analysis, comparative historical analysis, political claims analysis, socio-economic and cultural analysis, longitudinal survey analysis, interview based analysis, and photovoice techniques. It focuses in-depth on: (1) Border management and security, (2) International refugee protection, (3) Reception policies, (4) Integration policies, and (5) Conflicting Europeanization and externalization. We use these themes to examine multi-level governance while tackling the troubling question of the role of forced migration in precipitating increasing disorder in Europe. In contrast to much research undertaken on governance processes at a single level of analysis, RESPOND's multilevel, multi-method approach shows the co-constitutive relationship between policy and practice among actors at all three levels; it highlights the understudied role of meso-level officials; and it shines a light on the activities of non-governmental actors in the face of policy vacuums. Ultimately, RESPOND will show which migration governance policies really work

and how migrants and officials are making-do in the too-frequent absence of coherent policies. Adhering to a refugee-centered approach throughout, RESPOND will bring insights to citizenship, gender and integration studies, ensure direct benefit to refugee communities and provide a basis for more effective policy development.

Partners:

- 1 UPPSALA UNIVERSITET Sweden
- 2 THE GLASGOW CALEDONIAN UNIVERSITY United Kingdom
- 3 GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITÄT GÖTTINGENSTIFTUNG OFFENTLICHEN RECHTS Germany
- 4 THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF CAMBRIDGE United Kingdom
- 5 İSTANBUL BİLGİ UNIVERSİTESİ Turkey
- 6 SWEDISH RESEARCH INSTITUTE IN İSTANBUL Sweden
- 7 OZYEGIN UNIVERSİTESİ Turkey
- 8 UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI FIRENZE Italy
- 9 ΠΑΝΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΙΟ ΑΙΓΑΙΟΥ Greece
- 10 OESTERREICHISCHE AKADEMIE DER WISSENSCHAFTEN Austria
- 11 UNIWERSYTET WARSZAWSKI Poland
- 12 KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET Denmark
- 13 LEBANON SUPPORT Lebanon
- 14 THE HAMMURABI HUMAN RIGHTS ORGANIZATION, Iraq

Working Paper Series:

We are very excited to announce RESPOND's **Working Paper Series "Global Migration: Consequences and Responses"**. The Working Paper Series makes RESPOND results freely available to scholars and the general public in order to foster the exchange of ideas and collaboration within and beyond academia. We welcome paper proposals from all researchers working on similar topics.

The first set of papers analyze the socio-economic, political, legal and institutional context of migration governance in Austria, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iraq, Italy, Lebanon, Poland, Sweden, Turkey, the UK and the European Union as a whole. The papers are an incredible resource for scholars applying a comparative legal framework or for anyone seeking a deeper understanding of migration policy in Europe. series feature the most recent findings of the Project. The first 12 papers examine the legal and political context of migration governance in 11 countries and the EU.

Papers can be accessed at:

<https://www.crs.uu.se/respond/working-paper-series/>

RESPOND Blog:

The RESPOND Blog contains posts from the researchers. The goal of RESPOND is to study responses to mass migration to Europe in 2015 and afterward in order to provide a basis for more effective policy making. The project is an attempt to reckon with the sense of crisis that emerged due to migration movements and to generate recommendations for improving the governance capacity of the EU, member states and neighbors. RESPOND studies the key actors responsible for borders, protection, reception and integration while also addressing the broad issues of Europeanization and externalization. Employing a refugee-centered approach to the study of labor market integration, housing, citizenship and more, policy recommendations resulting from RESPOND will be relevant to refugees, effective and humane.

The blog is available at:

<http://responders.crs.uu.se/about-respond/>

RESPOND Newsletter

Respond Newsletter Series, which features recent stories from our blog, information about RESPOND researchers' activities, and upcoming events is available at: <https://www.crs.uu.se/respond>

Twitter: @RESPOND_H2020

Facebook: @RespondMigration

JEAN MONNET PROJECTS

FlipEU

The Jean Monnet Module entitled A 'Flipped Course' on EU is coordinated by Özge Onursal-Beşgül and Mehmet Ali Tuğtan. The FlipEU module is the first blended course on the EU and continues its second year in Istanbul Bilgi University. The module is delivered as a course under the General Education Curriculum with the course code and name GE 112 Introduction to European Union. The course utilizes the flipped classroom approach. This innovative teaching design allows the students to learn in their own time and at their own pace. The instructors deploy an instructional strategy and resources that place a higher order cognitive demand on the students, since the 'flipped' course engages the students with more creative, evaluative and analytical exercises.

The course provides an overview of the history, the evolving treaty framework, the political institutions, the decision-making processes and key policies of the European Union. The course addresses the questions related to particular choices of institutional design, policies and enlargement of the European Union in line with preferences and priorities of individual member states and the EU institutions as well as the changing international context. Students who successfully complete this course will be able to:

- to state the important turning points in the history of the European integration process;
- to explain the evolving treaty framework;
- to explain how the institutions of the European Union evolved;
- to analyse the contemporary issues in European integration process;
- to compare the European affairs of different member states.

The course is awarded the title of Jean Monnet Module by the European Commission and will be offered by Assistant Professors Özge Onursal-Beşgül in the fall semester and Mehmet Ali Tuğtan in the spring semester. The course will be offered within the framework of general education (GE) course elective list at BİLGİ.

Project Web site and Student Projects:

<https://flipeu.bilgi.edu.tr>

Living with indeterminacy: not deported but abandoned, being an undocumented migrant in İstanbul

**Ended on February 2018
Meltem Sancak Finke**

Migration and Hope: routes and transitions of global migration chains

“Routes of hope: Transitions and destinations in global migration flows” was the title of a workshop which was held in İstanbul, February 8-9, 2018. This meeting was also the final event of a two years project, which was hosted by the European Institute at İstanbul Bilgi University, and was co-funded by TÜBİTAK and the European Union. We started from the assumption that the movements of people and their decision to go, wait or stay is always filled and fuelled by “hope” for a better life not only for the individual migrant but also for the others who stayed at home. This hope is the inevitable company of migrants and their decision-making processes. At the same time, restrictive mobility regimes determine the lives of many migrants and make mobility only possible with the cost of human life and through dangerous journeys that we became familiar with in our daily news. Migration continues to constitute an important alternative and strategy for the improvement of livelihood and live in general.

During this fieldwork it turned out that an increasing number of Central Asian migrants are intending to stay in Turkey. Depending on gender, age and other factors there is a strong intention to establish a life for themselves alone or with other family members. Especially when other family members start to join them, schooling and further education of the children become an issue that must be taken care of. Especially the quality of education is one of the reasons why family reunification is considered and returning stops being an option for a better future of the children. The economic crisis, racism and deportation regime in Russia made Turkey an alternative route for Central Asian men, even though usually only less well-paid jobs are available for them. To take the route back home is associated with despair while hoping and trying at a new place is perceived more promising than other alternatives.

A family reunification and a coincidence at the same time: co-villagers meet in İstanbul

Turkey’s accessibility – regarding its geography, economy and visa regimen – makes it an attractive destination not only for my focus group Central Asians but also for other migrants from Africa and the Middle East, Latin America for any type of migration. Even if Turkey is a transit zone for some of

them who aim for other planned destinations in Europe, hope is the company of the migrant. Hope, as Phillip Mar (2005, 365) said, means that one can wait “for some object that can not be obtained in the present” but in the future; endurance, waiting and taking risks are further components of hope. Physical movement also allows imagining oneself as being socially on the move and escaping from the limitations at home, while living with the constraints of migration in the host country, especially if the migrant is undocumented. Migration continues to play a significant role in the practices and perceptions of a good and meaningful life in spite of uneasy challenges. It is simply a mean to reach “a meaningful life” or gives hope for “living”.

One critical variable held high is the distinction between different types of migration based on their presumed motivation for reasons of war, discrimination or poverty. But in all these different types of mobility the role of hope and despair is inherent. It starts from the idea or imagination of a good/better/bearable life somewhere else, which is essentially what makes people move and triggers mobility in most cases. During this process, some settle on the way, finding hope at some transitional spot like in İstanbul, while others keep moving towards an originally (un)planned destination (to Europe or beyond). Hope expresses future, perspectives and opportunities but also precarities, all highly related with mobility practices as strategies of improvement of livelihood. It is thus by inference that hopelessness of the present (at home) is it what creates migration aspirations. On their journey, people make use of existing or create new networks and institutions, which can be “hope-givers”, such as religious faiths or a state apparatus inviting them to come. These help people dealing with situations of risk and uncertainty to become tolerable. Institutions support existing hopes and create new ones, which promote a certain openness to risk taking for the uncertain but nevertheless expected. At the other end are the “hope-takers”, such as unfavorable visa regimes and labor regulations. However, unfulfilled expectations can also create despair, melancholy and “meaninglessness”. In this research, for some migrants İstanbul is a place of hope, no matter whether on transit or as permanent, one where a better future is possible. Mar, P. 2005. Unsettling potentialities: Topographies of hope in transnational migration.

Journal of Intercultural Studies 26 (4):361-378

SPECIAL GUEST

INTERVIEW WITH GÜLPERİ VURAL

Gülperi Vural worked at the European Institute as Project Manager between 2007 and 2018. She has greatly contributed to the Institute with her intellectual and administrative skills for eleven years. Having her with us has always made us feel confident in designing and undertaking so many different projects. She has been an inspiration to us all. We wish a bright future and thank her for eleven wonderful years of

friendship... She kindly accepted to answer a few questions for us and our readers... Here we go...

Ms. Gülperi Vural you have worked 11 years as the Administrative Coordinator and Project Manager for the European Institute at İstanbul Bilgi University. You retired as of April 2018: Let us begin with your thoughts and feelings. How do you feel?

In the beginning I felt a great loss for not being able to work and worried about what to do with my time. Before my work at the European Institute I had worked more than 31 years at the European Commission in Brussels. So this was my first experience in over 42 years, as a person without a job. But I have adjusted well to my new life. I immediately enrolled in academic courses at the Bogaziçi University to study subjects that I was interested in but never found time to study during my work. I also increased my physical training activities. Now I am at liberty to do things that please me. For the first time in my life I enjoyed a long holiday without worrying about my responsibilities in the Office. So I feel great.

Can you tell us about your experiences in the European Institute and BİLGİ?

Working in the European Institute and İstanbul Bilgi University was a great experience and pleasure. When offered this job, I had no experience in working at a purely Turkish and academic environment. So it was a challenge. At that period Turkey’s drive to join the European Union as a member was in full swing. We had to make the Institute one of the key players in this process. I believe that we were highly successful and the Institute played an important role in Turkey’s relations with the European Union.

In how many projects did you work and what is your unforgettable memory at the European Institute?

I did not count in how many projects I worked but it should be over fifty overall. When I look back now, I remember how we built an Institute with few resources and gained recognition and positive reputation in a relatively short time. This was made possible by the vision of the İstanbul Bilgi University and dedicated efforts of the team of the Institute. Being part of this great team is my most memorable experience.

Before you moved to İstanbul in 2007, you have worked for the EU Commission for many years. Can you tell us a little bit about how the EU Commission works? How is a regular day at the EU Commission?

After studying Political and Social Sciences at and graduating from the Brussels Free University, I had the intention of pursuing an academic career. But one of my Belgian Professors who had become a Commissioner guided me to joining in the European Commission as a member of the international staff. But this was not easy. As a Turkish national, joining the International Staff was not allowed. The chance came in when the European Commission allowed for an exception for one Turkish and one Greek national to join the International Staff after the Association Agreements with both countries. Until my early retirement from the Commission I was the only Turkish national who has worked at the Commission.

The European Commission divides its work among the Commissioners who are basically nominated by member countries with the agreement of the President of the Commission (and after hearings at the European Parliament), who himself is selected from the member states. Each Commissioner is given a certain area of responsibility. This responsibility is carried out through General Directorates. Such responsibilities or rather tasks include for instance enlargement, trade, competition, industry, agriculture etc. All

international staff allocated to the Directorates come from member states. The majority of this staff is permanent, while a small number are seconded from national governments. My regular day used to start very early in the morning and continued to late hours in the evening. Occasionally I had to work on weekends and travel a lot as well. International Staff members are also rotated among different General Directorates. For instance, I worked over the years in many different areas such as Press and Information, Informatics, Human Resources, Research, and Social Affairs. I feel very lucky and grateful for my long, varied and successful career at the European Commission where I was able to acquire a solid professional experience.

As one of your professional expertise is EU funded Projects, can you tell us in your opinion what the main indicators are to manage an EU funded Project successfully or what are the main challenges? Can you evaluate the EU funded Project management in Turkey?

During my time at BİLGİ’s European Institute, my key responsibility was in the area of EU funded projects. EU funded projects have contributed very much to the Europeanisation of the Turkish society, public and private sectors. The wave of EU funded projects which were launched in the past 15 years achieved a triple purpose: attaining important objectives in key areas of policy and infrastructure; helping train large groups of people in the related areas and in project management philosophy applicable to every work area, and, last but not least, disseminating universal values such as human rights, gender equality, freedom of press, protection of environment etc..

The efficient and effective management of EU funded projects is based on solid training of the involved parties in Project Management Cycle as well as the respect of certain basic management rules which are part of the daily functioning of every organisation in the EU.

The search for funding, the constitution of the Consortium or team which will present the project application, the careful and realistic preparation of the project application without any time pressure are all important aspects of the work involved in the selection of a project call and the preparation of the application.

In case of success, the timely preparation and signature of the Grant Agreement and starting the organisation of the team, and the workload are essential.

The classic indicators for the success of EU funded projects are, effective management, effective and well functioning teamwork, timely planning and execution of technical (content) and financial milestones, respect of obligations related to financial and technical reporting and focus on visibility, communication and dissemination. Periodic review of risks and challenges and alerting/consulting the EU Commission in case of any risks/challenges/difficulties in order to get feedback is also important.

Would you like to add anything you did not mention so far?

I am very proud and happy to have been part of BİLGİ’s European Institute. I have learned a lot and enjoyed my work within an excellent academic group committed to research.

I have also benefited very much from İstanbul Bilgi University’s excellent atmosphere. I feel very privileged to have known BİLGİ’s academics, management, research and administrative staff.

Thank you very much for sharing your thoughts with us and our readers...

CONFERENCES, ROUNDTABLES & WORKSHOPS

28-29 September 2017
CONFERENCE: “CRITICAL HERITAGES AND REFLEXIVE EUROPEANISATION”, BERLIN, GERMANY

The CoHERE mid-term conference entitled ‘Critical Heritages and Reflexive Europeanisation’ was held on 28th and 29th September 2017, at the Berlin Wall Memorial, Berlin. The conference was comprised of several presentations on culture, heritage, memory, identity and remembrance. The conference was a joint event with our ‘sister’ Horizon 2020 project, TRACES. If you would like to learn more about TRACES, please visit their website www.traces.polimi.it/

PROGRAM:

Thursday 28th - INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE | 1st day

08.45 - 09.15 | Registration
09.15 - 09.45 | Conference Opening and Welcome
09.45 - 10.30 | Project Presentations
10.30 - 11.45 | Cross-thematic Panel 1: “Heritage and Crisis” (1st session)
11.45 - 12.15 | Coffee break
12.15 - 13.15 | Cross-thematic Panel 2: “Performing heritage(s)” (1st session)
13.15 - 14.30 | Lunch break
14.30 - 15.45 | Cross-thematic Panel 3: “Performing heritage(s)” (2nd session)
15.45 - 17.00 | Cross-thematic Panel 4: “Neglected Heritages” (1st session)
17.00 - 17.30 | Coffee break
17.30 - 18.15 | Keynote Speech: Astrid Erll, Goethe-University Frankfurt am Main

Thursday 28th - INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE | 1st day

10.45 - 12.30 | Berlin Wall Memorial walking tour and opportunity for self-guided visit to exhibition
12.30 - 13.30 | Lunch break
13.30 - 15.00 | Roundtable “contentious Collections”
15.00 - 16.15 | Cross-thematic Panel 5: “Heritage and crisis” (2nd session)
16.15 - 16.45 | Coffee break
16.45 - 18.00 | Cross-thematic Panel 6: “Neglected Heritages” (2nd session)
18.00 - 18.30 | Closing Remarks

18-19 October 2017
TRIANGLE & FEUTURE PhD Workshop, 17&18 October 2017, BARCELONA, SPAIN

Under the theme “The European Union, Turkey and its wider neighbourhood: challenges and opportunities” on 17 and 18 October 2017, 11 PhD candidates from several countries took the chance to discuss their PhD theses with international experts such as Meltem Müftüler-Bac (Sabanci University), Robert Kissack (IBEL), Eduard Soler i Lecha (IBEL, CIDOB) and Atila Eralp (METU). The workshop was hosted by Institut Barcelona d'Estudis Internacionals and organized by TRIANGLE, funded by Stiftung Mercator and FEUTURE, funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme. Recurring topics in the discussion were narratives in the Turkish-German-EU relations, populism, and the theses' theoretical concepts.

18-19 October 2017
TRIANGLE & FEUTURE PhD Workshop, 17&18 October 2017, BARCELONA, SPAIN

On 19 and 20 October 2017, after 18 months of successful collaboration and joint research, the FEUTURE consortium met with distinguished Turkey experts, stakeholders from Turkey and the EU, the media and a wider interested public at the FEUTURE mid-term conference hosted by the Barcelona Centre for International Affairs (CIDOB) in Barcelona. The 77 participants enjoyed interesting and lively debates. The conference started with a keynote speech by Director-General for Neighbourhood and Enlargement Negotiation

of the European Commission, Christian Danielsson, taking stock of the state of the EU-Turkey relationship. This provided an excellent reference point for the two following panel discussions. Sinan Ülgen (EDAM), Angeliki Dimitriadi (ELIAMEP), Funda Tekin (Project Director, CETEUS / CIFE) and Meltem Müftüler-Bac (Sabanci University) engaged in a lively debate on the question “Drivers and brakes in EU-Turkey relations: ever-changing and ever-challenged?” moderated by Barçın Yinanç (Hürriyet Daily News). The contributions tackled the issues of public opinion in Turkey, migration policy, the relevance of the development of European integration as such and the applicability of the EU's enlargement policy as we know it. The results of this discussion also fed into the second panel on “What kind of f(e)uture scenario?” moderated by Piotr Zalewski (The Economist). Nathalie Tocci (Scientific Coordinator, IAI), Javier Nino Peres (EEAS), Nilgün Arisan Eralp (TEPAV) and Katharina Hoffmann (University of St. Gallen) discussed different options of how to frame EU-Turkey relations in the future. In spite of the current political debate the general conclusion was that cancelling accession negotiations would not help neither the EU and Turkey nor their relationship. The first day of the conference was concluded by a keynote speech by H.E. Ömer Önhon, Ambassador of Turkey to Spain.

The second day of the conference, 20 October 2017, was dedicated to the project's internal discussions in which researchers deepened their work within the particular Work Packages (Political Drivers, Economic Drivers, Security Drivers, Energy and Climate Drivers, Migration Drivers, Identity and Culture Drivers) and discuss the progress made so far and the steps still to be taken. FEUTURE's mid-term conference was closed by a concluding roundtable summarizing the most likely scenarios of the individual Work Packages and preparing the synthesis on the f(e)uture of the relationship that will be further substantiated by mid 2018.

1-2 December 2017
“KICK OFF MEETING AT UPPSALA UNIVERSITY”, UPPSALA, SWEDEN

All members of the RESPOND research team met at the first consortium meeting held at Uppsala University in Sweden, December 1-2, 2017. The meeting was chaired by Steering Committee member, Prof. Dr. Ayhan Kaya (İstanbul Bilgi University) in cooperation with the project coordinators, Assoc. Prof. Dr. Önvör A. Cetrez (Uppsala University) and Soner Barthoma, M.A. (Uppsala University). The gathering included a presentation of new research on polarization in Turkey by Prof. Dr. Murat Sömer, speeches from members of Uppsala University's Faculty of Theology, The Centre for Religion in Society and RESPOND's Advisory Board. The major part of the meeting was dedicated to sessions reviewing the administrative and financial management of the project, ethical guidelines, data management and each of the eight research Work Packages.

The researchers also spent significant time discussing two of the most exciting impact plans for the project: Advice Hubs for refugees in Iraq and Turkey and Migration Governance

Networks in each country. Through Advice hubs (Hope: Advice hub for refugees), RESPOND team members together with NGOs will provide legal and practical advice to refugees in transit conditions and help them to enter into the labour market by providing access to local companies willing to hire migrants. The Migration Governance Networks are designed to bring together the key stakeholders working on migration governance to enable them to contribute to and validate RESPOND's findings as well as to suggest solutions to some of the migration governance issues that RESPOND seeks to address.

27 December 2017
“POPULISM: FAR-RIGHT OR MAINSTREAM?”, ISTANBUL, TURKEY

On 27 December 2017, the European Institute organized a panel titled “Populism: Far-right or mainstream?” The panelists were Emre Erdogan, Ayhan Kaya and Ayse Tecmen. Emre Erdogan highlighted the abundance of theoretical discussions surrounding the nature of populism. Through an overview of his research on the extant literature he argued that populism can be considered a paradigm. His discussion informed the audience about the various approaches to the concept, which included the diverse conceptualisations of populism.

Ayhan Kaya discussed the findings from the CoHERE project, particularly the fieldwork conducted for WP2 exploring the role of the past for populist parties and movements' discourse. He gave a detailed overview of populist discourse in Europe and the common strategies they deploy to communicate with the public.

Ayşe Tecmen discussed public diplomacy and nation branding. She discussed the similarities among nation branding and populism as they can both be considered communications strategies. Based on the findings from the CoHERE project she examined Brand Turkey as a reflection of the populist discourse in Turkey.

8-9 February 2018
“ROUTES OF HOPE: TRANSITIONS AND DESTINATIONS IN GLOBAL MIGRATION FLOWS”, ISTANBUL, TURKEY

Final event of European Institute's TÜBİTAK Project “Living with indeterminacy: being an undocumented migrant in Istanbul”.

Venue: IFEA, Tomtom Mahallesi, Nur-i Ziya Sk. No:10, 34433 Beyoğlu/İstanbul

Convener: Meltem Sancak Finke, İstanbul Bilgi University

PROGRAM:

Day 1: February 8
Introduction: Migration and hope in and beyond Turkey

09:30 Bayram Balci (IFEA-Istanbul)

09:45 Ayhan Kaya (İstanbul Bilgi University-European Institute)

10:00 Meltem Sancak (Istanbul Bilgi University-EI, MPI Halle-Germany)
Central Asia(n)'s Gendered Directions of Hope
10:30 Discussion
11:00 Coffee Break

Syrian Dilemmas: Directions of hope, spaces of hopelessness

11:30 Duygu Topcu (Max Planck Institute Halle-Germany)
Re-negotiating gender roles: Syrian refugee families between hope and uncertainty
12:00 Souad Osseiran (Mercator Fell.-IPC Sabanci University, Istanbul)
Spaces of perseverance, spaces of hope: Syrian refugees' migrations to Europe
12:30 Discussion
13:00 Lunch Break

Hope and despair: Exclusion and deportation as migrant fates

14:30 Zahir Musa (Max Planck Institute Halle-Germany)
When hope turns to Despair: Narratives of Exclusion Practices of Migrants of Middle Eastern and African Backgrounds in Halle Saale, Germany
15:00 Dorte Thorsen (University of Sussex, UK)
Hope, deportation and death. Unexpected turns of migrant journeys from West Africa
15:30 Discussion
16:00 Coffee Break

Hope giver(s) in foreign land(s)

16:30 Dominik Müller (University of Zurich-ISEK)
Chancing Faces of Home-post-migrant everyday negotiations of islamic practice and belonging.
17:00 Armand Aupiais (Urmis (Paris Diderot), aMiMo (IFEA), Istanbul)
Hope as a ritual device in meso-level migration institutions. International immigrants' evangelical testimonies in Istanbul.
17:30 Discussion
18:30 Dinner

Day 2: February 9
Promising Homeland(s): the case of Kazak repatriates

09:30 Peter Finke (University of Zurich-ISEK)
Diffused hopes and despairs: Kazak repatriates from Mongolia
10:00 Indira Alibayeva Max Planck Institute Halle-Germany)
Between uncertainty and hope: ethnic return migration in Kazakhstan
10:30 Discussion
11:00 Coffee Break

Regimes of undoing hope: European migration politics

11:30 Andreas Dafinger (Central European University, Budapest)
Deterrence and Disillusionment. Approaches to international migration in Hungary (and beyond).
12:00 IGünther Schlee (Max Planck Institute Halle-Germany)
The Max Planck Initiative 'The Challenges of Migration, Integration and Exclusion': An Overview
12:30 Discussion
13:00 Closing remarks

12 February 2018
FEUTURE JOINT WORKSHOP OF WP6 AND WP7, ISTANBUL, TURKEY

FEUTURE researchers from the Work Packages (WP) 6 “Migration Drivers” and 7 “Identity and Culture Drivers” met on 12 February 2018 at Istanbul Policy Center/Sabanci University in Istanbul to discuss the research on drivers of EU-Turkey relations from these two thematic dimensions and to delineate the implications for the substantiation of a most likely scenario from their perspective. The WP members presented the results of their research in order to update their fellow WP partners and those of the cross-cutting WPs. In the discussion, several drivers and brakes were discussed in more detail. A special focus was put on drivers from the migration-identity nexus, i.e. possible overlaps between the Work Packages. One of the central questions in this context is whether recent migration flows have an influence on the identity discourses in Turkey and the EU. The researchers also discussed the possibility of a new wave of irregular migrants which could try to make their way from Turkey to Greece in the next months. This could potentially be a “wild card”, meaning a driver or change that could revise existing trends. Further, the research results from the partners in Egypt and Georgia were discussed who analysed the “outside” perspective from the Southern and Eastern neighbourhood for WP7. Their research shows that the migration deal had a (negative) influence on the perception of the EU and Turkey and their relationship from a US and Egyptian perspective. Lastly, the researchers discussed the research results in light of the task of delimiting a most likely scenario. For example, from WP6 perspective, it was outlined that according to the current state of the research, a cooperation scenario with potential of conflict due to diverging interests seems to be the most likely scenario.

2-3 March 2018
“A TASTE OF DIVERSITY”, BOLOGNA, ITALY

International conference organized by the Centro Interuniversitario di Storia culturale as part of the project “Critical Heritages: performing and representing identities in Europe”.

9 March 2018
EDUCATION AND HERITAGE IN MULTICULTURAL EUROPE, AARHUS, DENMARK

CoHERE’s work package 5, Heritage, Education and Identities, aims to develop best practices in the production and transmission of European heritages and identities within the two sectors that face challenges in an age of immigration and globalization, namely education and cultural heritage production. This workshop will investigate how European identity is shaped through formal and informal learning situations both in and outside the classroom.

3 April 2018
“KICK-OFF MEETING FOR RESPOND MULTILEVEL GOVERNANCE OF MASS MIGRATION IN EUROPE AND BEYOND”, ISTANBUL, TURKEY

The kick-off meeting for RESPOND: Multilevel Governance of Mass Migration in Europe and Beyond. RESPOND project funded by the European Commission under the Horizon2020 Programme was held on April 3rd, 2018 in Istanbul at the SR11. The meeting was organized jointly by the European Institute of Istanbul Bilgi University, the Swedish Research Institute in Istanbul (SR11), and Özyeğin University, which are the three partner organizations from Turkey within the RESPOND Consortium.

The aim of this meeting was to present the project and the team to stakeholders, and to start up a Migration Governance Network, which will allow better coordination and cooperation between the project team and related organizations. More than forty institutions, organisations and individuals were invited to the meeting based on their role in the priority areas of the RESPOND Project. The RESPOND Project aims to provide an in-depth understanding of the governance of recent mass migration at macro, meso and micro levels through cross-country comparative research and brings together 14 partners from 7 disciplines.

PROGRAM:

Part I (15:00- 16:30)

Welcome Speeches:

Therese Hydén (Consul General of Sweden)
 Dr. Kristina Josephson Hesse (Director, SR11)
 Dr. Ela Gökalp-Aras (Principle Investigator of RESPOND, SR11)
Moderator: Dr. Umur Korkut (Principle Investigator of RESPOND, Glasgow Caledonian University)

- “Presentation of RESPOND Project”, Dr. Ela Gökalp-Aras, Principle Investigator of RESPOND, SR11)
- “Current state of refugee studies in Turkey: Challenges and Prospects”, Prof. Ayhan Kaya (Principle Investigator of RESPOND, Istanbul Bilgi University)
- “Comparison of Mass Refugee Governance Patterns in Turkey, Lebanon and Jordan”, Dr. Zeynep Şahin-Mencütek (Senior Researcher of RESPOND)
- “Anthropological Research Methods for Refugee Studies”, Dr. Susan Rottmann (Principle Investigator of RESPOND, Özyeğin University)

Coffee Break (16:30- 16:45)

Part II (16:45- 18:00)

Moderator: Dr. Susan Rottmann (Principle Investigator of RESPOND, Özyeğin University)

- Voices from the Invitees (About ongoing/completed & planned projects or researches in the field of migration or related fields)
- Voices from the Syrian NGOs (Presentations by the Syrian NGOs from İstanbul, İzmir and Gaziantep)
- Open discussion to all participants

21-30 April 2018 CIFE'S SPRING ACADEMY: "TURKEY IN THE 21ST CENTURY", ISTANBUL, TURKEY

CIFE's Spring Academy "Turkey in the 21st century" was at BİLGİ. Lectures were given by Assist. Prof. Dr. Mehmet Ali Tuğtan, Department of International Relations, on "Contemporary Issues in the World Agenda: They Syrian Crisis and Beyond" and Halil Öz, Director of BİLGİ Incubation Center and participants from beneficiary NGOs, on "Innovation for the support of Civil Society". The lectures were followed by library studies.

Students enjoyed the nice weather in İstanbul with a city tour after the lectures and study trips.

27 April 18 FEUTURE MEETING, BRUSSELS, BELGIUM

On 27 April 2018, FEUTURE researchers of all work packages met in Brussels to discuss the results of the last two years. Researches summarised and discussed their main findings. The aim was to inform each other on the most likely scenario for overall EU-Turkey relations.

11-18-25 May 2018 "EUROPEAN INSTITUTE SPRING TALKS", ISTANBUL, TURKEY

The European Institute organized the first "Spring Talk" series inviting all BİLGİ students to discuss contemporary political and socio-cultural subjects. These talks took place on santralistanbul campus. Students had the opportunity to talk with their Professors in a warm atmosphere, share their opinions and ask their questions in an informal setting.

11 May: Ozan Kuyumcuoğlu, "Westernization and European Relations from Ottoman to Republic"

18 May: Gencer Özcan, "Current Situation in Syria"

25 May: Ayşe Tecmen, "Public Diplomacy and Formulation of Brand Turkey for EU Publics"

25 - 27 May 2018 "MEETING WITH RESPOND TEAM", GLASGOW, SCOTLAND-UK

The RESPOND project team was at Glasgow Caledonian University between 25 and 27 May 2018 to discuss the upcoming field research.

1 June 2018 "STUDENT PAPER COMPETITION: "GENDER EQUALITY IN THE LABOUR MARKET IN EUROPE AND TURKEY", ISTANBUL, TURKEY

Istanbul Bilgi University's European Institute invited BİLGİ students enrolled in BA and MA Programmes to a Paper Competition on the theme "Gender Equality in the Labour Market in Europe and Turkey" from 22 January 2018 to 01 June 2018.

The European Institute organised this competition in order to encourage all BİLGİ students to reflect and research on the comparative situations of women in the respective labour markets in Europe and Turkey. This challenging subject was analysed from many different aspects such as the state of gender equality regarding work, the legal framework/policies (including benefits, equal pay, maternity, measures in favour

of work/life balance), encouraging women's participation in the labour market, cultural differences per country/region, entrepreneurship, historical progress, the situation in public and private sectors, blue/white collar jobs and many others. The best papers were awarded prizes and are published at BİLGİ European Institute's website. The Winners of the Competition

Nihan Duran
"Dual Discrimination of Syrian Refugee Women in the Labour Markets in Europe and Turkey: Identifying the Challenges"

Verena Niepel
"Women in leadership positions in Germany and Turkey - A Comparison"
Papers are accessible at:
<https://eu.bilgi.edu.tr/en/>

21 - 24 June 2018 "MEDITERRANEAN MOBILITIES AND BORDERS", ISTANBUL, TURKEY

The European Institute of Istanbul Bilgi University in collaboration with Orient-Institute Istanbul organized a workshop entitled "Mediterranean Mobilities and Borders" between 21 and 24 June 2018 at the Orient-Institute Istanbul.

The workshop was part of an endeavor by the DFG-supported academic network "A Modern Mediterranean: Dynamics of a World Region, 1800-2000" and its partners to tie together the often disparate histories around the

Mediterranean to a history of the Mediterranean in modern times. Rather than postulating a unity and specificity of the region though, we understand the Mediterranean as a contact zone between Africa, Asia, and Europe, which is in turn intertwined with other spaces of interaction. Within this endeavor, the workshop aimed to clarify the nature and quality of mobilities around and across the modern Mediterranean as well as their limits.

With the advent of steamships, the region saw mobility on an unprecedented scale, accelerating the movement of goods, ideas, and people. Migratory movements, tourism, and pilgrimages evolved into mass phenomena, but so did the regulatory mechanisms aimed at curbing, channeling, or exploiting mobility. The workshop investigated the interactions and interdependencies of modern Mediterranean mobilities with aspects of power, with class, gender, and generational identities, and with images of the region. It aimed to develop a common perspective on these mobilities.

PROGRAM:

21 June 2018

19:00 Opening Talk Valeska Huber (Freie Universität Berlin) Channels of Communication: Connections and their Limits in the Suez Canal Region 1869-1914

21 June 2018

10:00 Words of Welcome / Introduction Melike Şahinli (Orient-Institut Istanbul), Manuel Borutta (Ruhr University Bochum), Malte Fuhrmann (Istanbul Bilgi University)

10:30 Avenues of Exploration in the Study of Mediterranean Interaction in History Chair: Esther Möller (UniBw Munich / Leibniz Institute of European History, Mainz) Nora Lafi (Leibniz Zentrum Moderner Orient, Berlin) Mediterranean Migration in Longue Durée Perspective Murat Dağlı (Istanbul Bilgi University) From Early-Modern to Modern: Where is the Mediterranean in Ottoman Historiography?

12:30 Lunch Break

14:30 Late Ottoman Landscapes and Entanglements Chair: Christian Saßmannshausen (Freie Universität Berlin) Paolo Giradelli (Boğaziçi University, Istanbul) Migrating Eastward at the Threshold of Modernity. Perspectives on the Italian - Ottoman Contact beyond the Trading Paradigm C. Ceyhan Arslan (Koç University, Istanbul) Theorizing the Mediterranean via Late Ottoman Travel Writings İlay Örs Romain (Istanbul Bilgi University) Cosmopolitan Enclaves Compared: Notes on Some Cultural Geographies in Istanbul Matthew Ghazarian (Columbia University, New York / Orient-Institut Istanbul) Communal Boundaries in the Ottoman East

23 June 2018

10:00 Moving, Being Moved, or Stranded around the Mediterranean Chair: Jasmin Daam (University of Kassel) Veruschka Wagner (Turkish-German University, Istanbul / SPP Transottomanica) Slaves of the Black Sea Region in Istanbul. Spatial and Social Mobility in the 17th Century Nicole Immig (Boğaziçi University, Istanbul) World War I and the Mediterranean: Some Thoughts on a New Research Field Daniel Tödt (Humboldt University, Berlin) Stranded in Marseille. Mediterranean Immobility and African Seafarers during World War II

12:30 Lunch Break

14:30 Flows and Blockages of Trans-Mediterranean Networks Chair: Fernando Esposito (Tübingen University)

Funda Soysal (Boğaziçi University, Istanbul) Galata going Global: The Istanbul Stock Exchange and 1895 South African Gold Mining Speculation Andreas Guidi (EHES, Paris / Humboldt University, Berlin) Translocal Networks on the Margins of International Law: Arms, Drugs, and Human Trafficking in the Mediterranean Region, 1870-1945 Alexis Rappas (Koç University, Istanbul) Building Interimperial Borders in the Eastern Mediterranean: Britain, Italy and France, 1920-1939

17:00 Final Discussion

18:00 Leisurely Stroll through Old Istanbul

27-28 September 2018 CoHERE WP2 WORKSHOP “EUROPEAN MEMORY AND POPULISM: REPRESENTATIONS OF SELF AND OTHER”, AMSTERDAM, the NETHERLANDS

The main aim of this workshop was to generate synergies and create strong connecting threads throughout the edited volume. The edited volume aims to explore the connection between memory and populism in its multiple facets. It focuses on circulating ideas of memory and especially of European memory in contemporary populist discourses of various kinds as well as populist ideas in sites and practices of remembrance that tend to go unmarked. Our broader theoretical aim is to reflect upon the similarities, differences, and slippages between memory, populism, nationalism, and cultural racism, that is, to reflect on the ways in which social memory contributes to give substance to various ideas of what constitutes the ‘people’ in populist discourse and beyond. The contributors discussed dominant notions of European heritage that circulate in the public sphere and in political discourse, and how the ‘politics of fear’ relates to such notions of European heritage and identity across and beyond Europe and the EU.

PROGRAM:

Thursday 27 September

9:30 -10:00 Opening Talk Valeska Huber (Freie Universität Berlin) Channels of Communication: Connections and their Limits in the Suez Canal Region 1869-1914

10:00 - 10:15 Welcome and Opening, Ayhan Kaya and Chiara De Cesari

10:15 - 11:15 Chiara De Cesari: ‘(Why) do Eurosceptics believe in a common European heritage?’
Discussant: Markus Balkenhol

11:15 - 12:15 Tuuli Lähdesmäki: ‘European Culture, History, and Heritage as Political Tools in the Rhetoric of the Finns Party’

Discussant: Gal Kirn

12:15 - 13:30 Lunch

13:30 - 14:30 Ayhan Kaya and Ayşe Tecmen: ‘The Use of the Past in Populist Political Discourse: Justice and Development Party Rule in Turkey’

Discussant: Luiza Bialasiewicz

14:30 - 15:30 Luiza Bialasiewicz and Lora Sariaslan: ‘The texture(s) of memory: Rugs and the materialities of urban fears’

Discussant: Ayşe Tecmen

15:30 - 16:00 Coffee break

16:00 - 17:00 Pawel Karolewski: ‘Memory Games and Populism in Postcommunist Poland’

Discussant: Susannah Eckersley

17:00 - 18:00 Final discussion opened by Paul Mepschen

19:00 Drinks and dinner

Friday 28 September

10:00 - 11:00 Susannah Eckersley: ‘Between appropriation and appropriateness: instrumentalising dark heritage in populism and memory?’

Discussant: Lora Sariaslan

11:00 - 11:15 Coffee

11:15 - 12:15 Gönül Bozoğlu: “‘A great bliss to keep the sensation of conquest alive!’
The emotional politics of the Panorama 1453 Museum in Istanbul’

Discussant: Ayhan Kaya

12:15 - 13:15 Gal Kirn: ‘Anti-totalitarian Monuments in Ljubljana and Brussels: From Nationalist Reconciliation to Open Rehabilitation of Fascism’

Discussant: Gönül Bozoğlu

13:15 - 14:15 Lunch

14:15 - 15:15 Hilla Dayan: ‘Mizrahi Memory of- and Memory-against “the People:” remembering the 1950s’

Discussant: Chiara De Cesari

15:15 - 15:30 Coffee

15:30 - 16:30 Markus Balkenhol: ‘Caring for some and not Others: Museums and the politics of care in post-colonial Europe’

Discussant: Hilla Dayan

16:30 - 17:30 Final discussion opened by Paul Mepschen and wrap up

8 October 2018

“HOW DIPLOMACY MAKES AND UNMAKES PEACE” BY PROF. DR. MARKUS KORNPBST, ISTANBUL, TURKEY

The European Institute and Department of International Relations of Istanbul Bilgi University in collaboration with Austrian Cultural Forum Istanbul organized a seminar delivered by Prof. Dr. Markus Kornprobst about “How Diplomacy Makes and Unmakes Peace”.

PROGRAM:

14:00 Welcome

Prof. Dr. Ayhan Kaya – İstanbul Bilgi University, Director of European Institute, Jean Monnet Centre of Excellence, Department of International Relations

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Emre Erdoğan – İstanbul Bilgi University, Head of Unit, Department of International Relations

14:15 Seminar: “How Diplomacy Makes and Unmakes Peace”

15:15 Q&A

Professor Markus Kornprobst holds the Chair in International Relations at the Diplomatic Academy of Vienna. He previously taught at the School of Public Policy at University College London and Magdalen College at Oxford University. He held research fellowships at the Mershon Center at the Ohio State University, and the Department of Politics and International Relations at Oxford University. His research appears in leading journals in the discipline such as International Organization, European Journal of International Relations, International Studies Review, Review of International Studies, and Millennium. He is the author of Irredentism in European Politics (Cambridge University Press) and co-editor of Metaphors of Globalization (Palgrave).

PUBLICATIONS

- Atamer, Y. Article: (Together with Mirjam Eggen, Reformbedürftigkeit des schweizerischen Kaufrechts – eine Übersicht’ [The Need to Reform the Swiss Sales Law - An Overview], Zeitschrift des Bernischen Juristenvereins (ZBJV), 11/2017, pp. 731-787.

- Atamer, Y. Book chapter: ‘Ceza Koşulu – Götürü Tazminat-Sorumsuzluk Anlaşması: Hangisi? Karşılaştırmalı Hukuk Işığında Sözleşmelerin Yorumlanmasında Bazı Tutamak Noktaları’ [Penalty, Liquidated Damages or Exemption Clause? Interpretation Guidelines in Light of Comparative Law], Atamer/Baş Süzal/Geisinger (eds.), Uluslararası İnşaat Sözleşmelerinde Gecikme ve Temerrüt – Eski Bir Soruna Yeni Çözümler, XII Levha Yayıncılık, İstanbul, 2018, pp. 87-131.

- Atamer, Y. Book chapter: Commentary of Arts 78-80 CISG in: UN-Convention on Contracts for the International Sale of Goods (CISG), Kröll/Mistelis/Perales Viscasillas (eds.), C. H. Beck, Hart, Nomos Publishers, 2nd ed., 2018, pp. 1027-1089.

• Atamer, Y. Edited book: (With Ece Baş Süznel and Elliott Geisinger) Uluslararası İnşaat Sözleşmelerinde Gecikme ve Temerrüt - Eski Bir Soruna Yeni Çözümler [Delays in International Construction Contracts - New Approaches to an Eternal Issue], XII Levha Yayıncılık, İstanbul, 2018, XXXIV + 326 pp.

• Doğan Yenisey, K. Editörlük (Seda Ergüneş Emrağ ile) "İş Hukukunda Yeni Yaklaşımlar", Beta Yayınları. 2017.

• Doğan Yenisey, K. ve Mahmut Kabakçı "Gönüllü Emeği ve İş Hukuku", İstanbul Bilgi Üniversitesi Yayınları. 2017.

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• Kaya, A. Populism and Heritage in Europe: Lost in Diversity and Unity. Routledge forthcoming 2019.

• Kaya, A. And Ayşe Tecmen Critical Analysis Tool (CAT) 3: Islam versus Europe: Populist discourse and the construction of a civilizational identity (2018).

• Kaya, A. Turkish Origin Migrants and their Descendants: Hyphenated Identities in Transnational Space. London: Palgrave (2018).

• Kaya, Ayhan (2017). Populismo e Immigration en la Union Europea," in J. Arango, R. Mahia, D. Moha and E. Sanchez-Montijano (eds.), La inmigración en el oja del horacan. Anuario CIDOB de la inmigración. Barcelona: CIDOB: 52-79
Kaya, Ayhan (2018), "Right to the City: Insurgent Citizens of the Occupy Gezi Movement", in Didem Buhari Gülmez (ed.), Bridging Divides. London: Routledge.

• Kaya, Ayhan (2018), "Right-Wing Populism and Islamophobia in Europe and their Impact on Turkey-EU Relations," Turkish Studies, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14683849.2018.1499431>

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PROGRAMMES ON EUROPEAN STUDIES

BİLGİ MA IN EUROPEAN STUDIES

The MA Program, launched in 2000 and run by the Social Sciences Institute, is designed to provide a thorough knowledge of the European Union, its historic development, its institutions, systems and policies. Turkey's longstanding EU integration process, which started in 1963, continued with the Customs Union (1996) that made Turkey part of the European Single Market. Within the framework of the program, Turkey's EU accession period is analyzed and researched with a focus on recent developments. The Program, concentrating on themes such as enlargement and the societal transformations it brings to the countries involved (peace, stability, democratization, regional cooperation, human rights, rule of law, etc.) and European Neighborhood Policy, also offers a wider perspective of European Studies with emphasis on issues such as migration, environmental issues and intercultural dialogue.

For further information please visit: <http://eustudies.bilgi.edu.tr/>

DOUBLE DEGREE MA IN EUROPEAN STUDIES (BİLGİ - EUROPA-UNIVERSITÄT VIADRINA)

EUROPA-
UNIVERSITÄT
VIADRINA
FRANKFURT
(ODER)

As one of the core countries of European integration since the early days of the European Coal and Steel Community, Germany with its political, social and economic structure deserves special attention in studies regarding the European Union. To this end, the European Institute of İstanbul Bilgi University has developed close relations with many universities and institutes in Germany. The academic cooperation with the European University Viadrina is an exemplary relationship, which started as a two-way exchange of students and academics, leading finally to an enhanced collaboration agreement between the two universities funded by the German Foreign Academic Exchange Service (DAAD). Graduates not only gain an insight into life in two very different European cities, but also prepare themselves for a rapidly changing world of work across the European continent. The program is run by the Social Sciences Institute.

With 30% of foreign students from over 70 countries and an extensive network of partner universities, European University Viadrina is one of the most international universities worldwide. The study courses and university degrees are internationally acknowledged. Its atmosphere is personal and warm, and with excellent student support and guidance European University Viadrina is able to offer outstanding study conditions. Viadrina is located at the

German-Polish border, only one hour by train from Germany's capital, Berlin.

The University's proximity to Poland and to Eastern Europe is clearly a distinctive feature of the degree program. Students are able to both learn about the expansion of Europe to the east whilst actively experiencing life on both sides of the German-Polish border. In addition, extensive supervision is offered, along with small seminar groups and outstanding technical facilities. Should Frankfurt be too small, then there is always Berlin, only an hour away by train.

For further information please visit: <http://maesdd.bilgi.edu.tr/>

MASTER IN ADVANCED EUROPEAN AND INTERNATIONAL STUDIES - MAEIS

Applications for the "Master in Advanced European and International Studies" (MAEIS) at CIFE's Institut européen-European Institute (IE-EI) (Nice/France) in cooperation with İstanbul Bilgi University's European Institute are open. The Master's programme offers the unique opportunity to learn about the challenges and chances of Europe and develop perspectives for its future by learning and living in different European countries over the year. The MAEIS is a one-year-programme that takes place in three different study locations. The programme includes semesters in different countries, complemented by a study trip to the European and international organisations in Strasbourg, Brussels and Geneva.

For further information please visit: [www.ie-ei.eu](http://www.ie-ei.eu/en/3/description_21-1)
http://www.ie-ei.eu/en/3/description_21-1

FROM OUR STUDENTS

VERENA NIEPEL, DOUBLE DEGREE MA IN EUROPEAN STUDIES

Soon it will be ten months that I spend mostly in İstanbul. I came to Turkey for the first time as a student of European Studies from the Viadrina University in Frankfurt (Oder) (Germany). I remember when I was accepted for the double Master's program one year prior to actually going to İstanbul, my first reaction was just excitement. The development of the political situation in Turkey 2016 started a phase of reconsidering my decision. Back then, I was working in German media and I experienced how many Turkish

journalists came to Berlin to look for shelter. Still I wanted to go to understand what is happening. My curiosity made me come to İstanbul and now I even stayed longer than just for the Masters program. The more people I talked to and the better my Turkish became, the more I understood of what moves people in my environment.

Courses at İstanbul Bilgi University supported this understanding. It is still one of the top rated universities and I experienced that in all of my courses. The teachers were all motivated to teach but also they appreciated the students' opinions and provided room for discussions. Although the content of the courses, such as Politics of Cultural Diversity in the European Union or Turkish Foreign Policy was informative and enriching, I also learned from the other students. I met people from different countries and continents in my classes, even from Mexico and Kyrgyzstan! To hear different views and opinions was very special. Although unfortunately not that many young people from Turkey joined the English speaking courses, the few Turkish students were open and eager to share their perspectives. This really widened my horizon. Also I took a course in the Architecture department about urban infrastructure and social space, which added a new angle to my studies of the European society. The education in BİLGİ is overall eye-opening. On the other hand, I also think about what I heard about the difficult situation of the academics at BİLGİ. Many seemed to have left either to go to military service or to go to Europe. This was the sad part. The research for my Master thesis on visual artists, who recently moved from İstanbul to Berlin, strengthened this impression of a deep depression in many parts of a privileged, educated class in İstanbul. This is probably also true for other parts of society, but what I know from talking directly to people is limited to the 20-30 years old in my private surrounding.

After I was done with my thesis, I continued with an internship at the Orient Institute in İstanbul from September on. It feels though like those kind of possibilities became rare and for me it is clear that I will leave the country after my work at the institute. Although there are still social and spatial spaces where one can be free in İstanbul, the longer I stayed here, the heavier became the weight of the despair of my friends on my shoulders. Still, the BİLGİ Campus is a good example for being able to escape the tumult and oppression. Bordering a rather poor area in materialistic terms, it is a green space of recreation accessible for all.

FATİH ETKE, MA IN EUROPEAN STUDIES

During my bachelor studies in İstanbul Bilgi University, I had a chance to get acquainted with BİLGİ's education culture, academic stuff, and campus life. I am very lucky to have taken the course from respected professors in their fields. The success of İstanbul Bilgi University particularly in social sciences is certificated by authorities, and I believe that the main reason behind this success is its innovative, and student-centred education culture. I also took an active role

in the student clubs during my 4-years as an undergraduate student at Bilgi University. I am one of the founders of the European Union Student Club, and I am still in contact with the club administration staff. Particularly, the variety and quality of the courses in our department has been the most effective driving force for me to continue to work in this field. Furthermore, the positive correlations between European Studies courses and our Club's projects/events helped me decide to pursue an academic career.

As a graduate student with honours, I continued my MA in European Studies at Bilgi University as well. One of the most important reasons why I would like to remain in this University is that I have already had an information about the MA programs. Also, I wanted to study migration crisis and populism, which have strong links to European Studies. Additionally, I was tandem partner for exchange students, so I knew how fit European Studies to my interested field. Furthermore, BİLGİ has a Double Degree in European Studies with Viadrina University. This program provides a very productive exchange-student experience. Students can study two semesters in Viadrina after having two semesters at BİLGİ. After completing the program, students receive two diplomas from each university. After having very interesting courses at BİLGİ, I had the opportunity to take current "neo-Nationalism" and "Populism" courses in the Viadrina University as well. These courses shaped and crystalized my thesis. This is a very well-designed program in which I have not encountered any problem. Also, Viadrina University has amazing international environment where people from all around the world came together and share their knowledge and experiences.

DEMET EKIN DORUK, BA IN EUROPEAN UNION RELATIONS

The following is an opinion piece written by our intern Demet Ekin Doruk who is a 4th year student in the European Union Relations Undergraduate Program.

Universalizing "Shared Differences" through street arts

In order to detach from politics and other distance, it is necessary to universalize art a little. Therefore, the name of my wall art on the French Cultural Center is "Shared Differences". Jef Aerosol. (Born in France in 1957, Jef Aerosol is a painter whose interest is on street art).

While acknowledging that the convergence of groups with different historical, cultural, political and social backgrounds

leads to tensions from time to time, it is quite realistic to expect that this coming together will create an environment of mutual trust and understanding. Because at the end of the day, what will keep societies alive is that differences coexist through tolerance.

If the tendency to resist differences does not leave any place for tolerance for the virtues of human beings, the tensions will always lead to conflicts that will challenge our conception of modernity which is centred on respect for differences.

This is a very peaceful way of dealing with the differences between Turkey, which has been a candidate for EU membership since the Helsinki summit of 1999, and other members of the Union. Considering the diversity within territorially-bound countries, it is quite natural to encounter a variety of differences when we go beyond the borders and consider the EU's various member states. Instead of seeing this diversity as a threat, it is a peaceful approach to see it as an integrative value.

In other words, it is integral to recognize that our differences create a beautiful portrait when we recognize the colourful nature of diversity. Because our fundamental common characteristic is that we are all different from each other.

When we look at today's world maps where human beings have existed for thousands of years, especially with the borders drawn after 1945, we can realize that different people share the same structures in different places. Even somewhere across the globe, it is very easy to find something from yourself or from your surroundings. This is quite natural and human. Because mankind subconsciously seeks that which is familiar. As we know this is an existential issue, a reflex rooted in our survival instinct. So, it's always easier to discover the similarities.

But there is something we tend to overlook, and I think that this is the real point that will create an atmosphere of trust and peace in today's world.

As we observe different people share the same habits in different corners of the world, when we expand our perspective a little more, we realize that the unique differences of the different societies we see in the different corners of the world have the same quality. To be different from one another... So, we can look at the differences as uniqueness and discover its value and beauty. In my opinion, the easiest method to provide an atmosphere of peace in today's world is to share a culture of tolerance.

French artist Jef Aerosol's work on the wall of the French Cultural Center in Izmir shared the same sentiments. He expressed his intentions behind this artwork as:

"People viewing my murals in Izmir can have different reactions to the interactions of Turkey and France. Here we aimed to bring tolerance to the foreground. Turkey and France are two very beautiful place." (<http://www.hurriyet.com.tr/paylasilan-farkliliklari-cizdi-40478589>)

As I noted earlier, rather than believing that differences are detrimental, if we succeed in looking at the world from a different perspective where differences have added value, then we can separate art from political discourses. We need to acknowledge that politics is an intellectual method which is a strategic means to an end. If we succeed in separating arts from politics then we can allow art to exist on its own value, rather than a political statement.

.... and if you ever visit Izmir, take a tour around the French Cultural Center and don't forget to see the Shared Differences mural.

- We are very proud, but also sad, to announce that **Prof. Dr. Yeşim Atamer**, vice-director of our Institute since 2007, will continue her carrier as a professor of private law at Bern University, Faculty of Law as of February 2019. We are sure that Professor Atamer will retain close ties to Bilgi University where she worked for 18 years and has contributed greatly to the institutionalization of the Law Faculty and of the European Union Institute.

- **Gülperi Vural** who has worked at Istanbul Bilgi University's European Institute as the Administrative Coordinator for 11 years retired in April 2018. The European Institute is grateful to Ms. Vural for the successful work she carried out at the Institute and wish her the best in her future endeavors.

- **Dr. Malte Fuhrmann** who has worked at the European Institute for 2 years as a DAAD (German Academic Exchange Service) Fellow will continue his career as a Researcher in Leibniz-Zentrum Moderner Orient Berlin. The European Institute is thankful to Dr. Fuhrmann for the work he carried out at BİLGİ and wish him the best in his future career.

- **Aslı Aydın-Sancar** who was in charge of the Education Programs was promoted to the post of Project Manager of the European Institute in April 2018. The European Institute congratulates her and wishes her all the best in her new post.

- **Didem Balatlıoğulları**, who graduated from İstanbul Bilgi University Management of Performing Arts department, started to work as the Administrative Assistant of the Institute in April 2018. The European Institute welcomes her and wishes all the best in her new post.

- We are proud to announce that our Double Degree MA in European Studies Programme alumni **Dominik Pollner's** thesis "Europe's Gatekeeper: a dialectical analysis of Turkey's signing of the March 2016 Agreement" was awarded the GTOT (Gesellschaft für Turkologie, Osmanistik und Türkeiforschung) Prize 2018 for outstanding works in the field of Turkish Studies at the 3rd European Convention on Turkic, Ottoman and Turkish Studies organized by the Society for Turkic, Ottoman and Turkish Studies.

Founded in 1996 with the motto 'learn for life, not for school', İstanbul Bilgi University is a city university intertwined with İstanbul's vibrant cultural life and in close connection with the business world. BİLGİ is renowned for qualified international education and career opportunities as the only member of Laureate International Universities in Turkey.

Since its founding, BİLGİ has attempted to establish a cultural and scientific community that promotes tolerance and respect for a diversity of individuals with different lifestyles, beliefs and ways of thinking within the framework of contemporary universal values, while at the same time maintaining strong ties with all segments of society. The BİLGİ community includes more than students: it also includes faculty, alumni, families, employers and neighboring communities where BİLGİ is located. Today BİLGİ represents a sound and distinct attitude in the academic and intellectual life in Turkey with its more than 35,000 graduates, more than 20,000 students and more than 1,000 academic staff.

Functioning under the aegis of the Turkish Council of Higher Education, BİLGİ is an individual full member of the European University Association (EUA) and a member of the International Association of Universities (IAU). With more than 500 exchange agreements in Europe, BİLGİ is also an active participant in the Erasmus exchange network and has strong academic affiliations with numerous universities abroad. In 2006, BİLGİ joined the Laureate International Universities network, which provides quality higher education on an international scale with more than 60 accredited campus-based and online universities throughout North America, Latin America, Europe, Northern Africa, Asia and the Middle East. With this collaboration, BİLGİ students are able to be a part of an educational network which includes the University of Roehampton in the UK, Kendall College in US, Santa Fe University of Art and Design, San Diego NewSchool of Architecture and Design, Walden University, Business, Information and Technology School in Germany, Universidad Del Valle de Mexico and Universidad Europea de Madrid in Spain.

BİLGİ seeks to educate freethinking, creative, intellectually curious and enterprising individuals who will contribute to a world in which knowledge is the primary driving force in society, where knowledge is accessible to all and, indeed, in which access to it has come to be seen as a fundamental human right. BİLGİ holds a primary responsibility for providing, maintaining and further developing an academic environment in which both students and faculty members are able to engage in learning and the production of knowledge at the highest level. BİLGİ offers more than 200 programs in its six faculties, five institutes, five schools and three vocational schools that provide education to its associate, undergraduate and graduate students. The medium of instruction at BİLGİ is English. Before being admitted to their degree programs, students must demonstrate their proficiency in English. Students whose level of English is not sufficient to begin undergraduate study will have to enroll in the English Preparatory Program.

BİLGİ has three innovative campuses on the European side of İstanbul, the 2010 European Capital of Culture. Located in central neighborhoods, the three BİLGİ campuses - **santral**İstanbul, Kuştepe and Dolapdere - offer easy access to social and cultural activities in İstanbul. Kuştepe Campus is located in Şişli, the center of İstanbul's business

life, and Dolapdere Campus, an award-winning campus for its architectural design, is only ten minutes away from Taksim, the heart of the art scene, social activities and city life. **santral**İstanbul Campus is an arts and culture complex located along the Golden Horn, hosting more than 700 conferences, festivals and other scientific and social events a year and includes the Energy Museum, Main Gallery, as well as educational buildings.

ACADEMIC PROGRAMMES

FACULTIES

Faculty of Architecture

Architecture
Industrial Design
Interior Design

Faculty of Business

Business Administration
Business Informatics
Business-Economics
Economics
Economics and Finance (Honors)
Economics and Management (Honors)
International Finance
International Trade and Business
Marketing

Faculty of Communication

Advertising
Arts and Cultural Management
Communication Design and Management
Cultural Management*
Digital Game Design
Film and Television
Management of Performing Arts
Media and Communication
Photography and Video
Public Relations
Visual Communication Design
Television Reporting and Programming

Faculty of Engineering and Natural Sciences

Civil Engineering
Computer Engineering
Computer Sciences
Electrical and Electronics Engineering
Energy Systems Engineering
Genetics and Bioengineering
Industrial Engineering
Mathematics
Mechanical Engineering
Mechatronics Engineering

Faculty of Health Sciences

Child Development
Health Management
Nursing
Nutrition and Dietetics
Occupational Therapy
Perfusion
Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation

Faculty of Law

Law

Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities

Comparative Literature
English Language Teacher Education
European Union Studies
History
International Relations
Music
Political Science
Psychology
Sociology

SCHOOLS

School of Applied Sciences

Banking and Finance
Fashion Design
International Logistics and Transportation

School of Aviation

Aviation Management

School of Sports Sciences and Technology

Sports Management

School of Tourism and Hospitality

Gastronomy and Culinary Arts
Tourism and Hotel Management

ASSOCIATE DEGREE PROGRAMS

School of Advanced Vocational Studies

Accounting and Tax Applications*
Architectural Restoration*
Education)
Banking and Insurance*
Civil Air Transportation Management**
Civil Aviation Cabin Services*
Computer Programming
Construction Technology*
Cooking*
Cyber Security
Fashion Design*
Graphic Design*
Interior Space Design
International Trade
Media and Communication Technologies
Printing and Publishing Technologies
Public Relations and Advertising

Vocational School of Health Services

Anesthesia*
Audiometry*
Child Development*
Dental Prosthetics Technology*
Dialysis*
Electroneurophysiology*
Emergency and Disaster Management
First and Emergency Aid*
Occupational Health and Safety*
Operating Room Services*
Opticianry*
Oral and Dental Health*
Pathology Laboratory Techniques*
Physiotherapy*
Social Services

Vocational School of Justice

Justice

* The program has evening education

MASTER PROGRAMS

Institute of Graduate Programs

Accounting and Auditing
Architectural Design
Banking and Finance *
Clinical Psychology
Construction Management *
Cultural Management
Cultural Studies
Double Degree MA in European Studies (İstanbul Bilgi University and Europa-Universität Viadrina Frankfurt-Oder)
Economics
Electrical-Electronics Engineering
European Studies
Film and Television
Financial Economics
History *
History, Theory and Criticism in Architecture
Human Resource Management
Information and Technology Law
International Finance
International Political Economy
International Relations
Joint LL.M in Turkish-German Business Law (İstanbul Bilgi University-Cologne University)
Law (Business Law/Human Rights Law)
LITE / Entrepreneurship and Innovation in Technology
Marketing
Marketing / Next Academy
Marketing Communication
MBA
Media and Communication Systems
Nutrition and Dietetics
Organizational Psychology
Philosophy and Social Thought
Public Relations and Corporate Communication
Social Projects and NGO Management *
Trauma and Disaster Mental Health

Online Master Programs

Banking and Finance Online
e-MBA Turkish
e-MBA English
Health Management Online *
Human Resources Management Online
Management Information Systems Online

DOCTORAL PROGRAMS

Graduate School of Sciences Programs

PhD in Economics *
PhD in Communication *
PhD in Business Administration *
PhD in Public Law *
PHD Private Law *
PhD in Political Science *

* No intake for 2018-2019 Academic Year

SPECIAL SECTION DEDICATED TO THE COHERE PROJECT

WHAT IS CoHERE?

Critical Heritages: performing and representing identities in Europe (CoHERE) seeks to identify, understand and valorise European heritages, engaging with their socio-political and cultural significance and their potential for developing communitarian identities. CoHERE addresses an intensifying EU Crisis through a study of relations between identities and representations and performances of history. It explores the ways in which heritages can be used for division and isolation, or to find common ground and 'encourage modern visions and uses of its past.' The research covers a carefully selected range of European territories and realities comparatively and in depth; it focuses on heritage practices in official and non-official spheres and engages with various cultural forms, from the living arts to museum displays, food culture, education, protest, commemorations and online/digital practice, among others. CoHERE is funded through Horizon 2020 and responds to the Reflective Societies programme. CoHERE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 693289.

'HERITAGE' AND 'HERITAGES'

We take a broad but delimited understanding of heritage (mindful of the notorious difficulty of assigning a consensus definition) as a representational, discursive and performative practice involving conscious attempts to valorise aspects of the past in the present. Within the purview of CoHERE, heritage can be official or unofficial, tangible or intangible, or mixtures of these. It may not always be a social good productive of perceived-to-be progressive identities, respectful intergroup relations or benign moral positions, suggesting the existence of plural 'heritages' that are sometimes in conflict with one another, rather than a monolithic 'common heritage'. Likewise, contemporary connections with events, cultures and sites from prehistory to the recent past may all be important for identity construction, and this is recognised in the temporal depth of the research.

Key aims of the research

1. To interrogate the meanings, frameworks and expressions of European heritages both in theory, practice and policy;
2. To develop relational perspectives on heritages and cultural politics in Europe;
3. To provide intellectual, creative cultural and practical instruments (including digital ones) for valorising European heritages and promoting communitarian identities.

Key approaches

1. The relational study of productions and experiences of heritage at institutional, social and personal levels, including research into people's activities and attitudes;
2. Research by practice and the provision of public-facing dissemination activities;
3. The critically-informed development of instruments (e.g. models for policy, curricula, museum and heritage practice) intended to promote reflection on and valorisation of European heritages and to engender socially-inclusive attitudes.
4. The project is multidisciplinary, including museum, heritage and memory studies, cultural history, education, musicology, ethnology, political science, archaeology, ethnolinguistics and digital interaction design. The consortium comprises 12 partners over 9 countries, including universities, an SME, two museums and a cultural network. The research covers diverse European territories and realities comparatively and in depth.

The Consortium

1. Newcastle University (coordinator), UK
2. Aarhus University, Denmark
3. University of Amsterdam, Netherlands
4. National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece
5. İstanbul Bilgi University, European Institute, Turkey
6. University of Bologna, Italy
7. Copenhagen Institute of Interaction Design, Denmark
8. Heriot-Watt University, UK
9. Latvian Academy of Culture, Latvia
10. European Network of Cultural Centres, Belgium
11. POLIN Museum of the History of Polish Jews, Poland
12. Tropenmuseum, Netherlands

OBJECTIVES OF CoHERE?

Overarching project objectives are to:

- Critically review and theorise key concepts, such as 'European heritages', 'European identity' and 'collective memory' in relation to academic literature, museum and heritage practice, value cultures, politics and policy and EU structures and agendas.
- Understand the reach and purchase of 'European heritages' and 'European identities' and assess their challenges as well as the opportunities they contain for peaceful and communitarian social relations in Europe.
- Investigate how and why symbolic representations and performances construct ideas of place, history and heritage, tradition and belonging in Europe, identifying which of these representations and performances count as European heritage, to whom, where and when.
- Analyse, through key examples (e.g. musics, food, histories, curricula), how heritage representations 'travel' between different institutional, social and personal spheres and how identities are negotiated and produced through this.
- Explore how and why relationships with and attitudes to the past inform identity positions, social orderings and moral values in Europe.

• Identify and propose governmental, policy, institutional, educational and community-linked heritage strategies that sustain and equitably transmit core social values of the EU.

• Disseminate the research in numerous spheres and develop instruments that demonstrate and model its application, reaching diverse communities from policy makers and museum, heritage and education professionals to different publics, including children.

CoHERE Work Packages

CoHERE has 8 Work Packages, among these the following six are research-based, and the remaining two are management and dissemination.

WP1 Productions and omissions of European heritage

Productions and omissions of European heritage provides a critical foundation for CoHERE as a whole, interrogating different meanings of heritage, historical constructions and representations of Europe, formative histories for European identities that are neglected or hidden because of political circumstances, and non-official heritage.

WP2 The use of past in political discourse and the representation of Islam in European museums

The use of past in political discourse and the representation of Islam in European museums investigates public/popular discourses and dominant understandings of a homogeneous 'European heritage' and the exclusion of groups such as minorities from a stronger inclusion into European society. The WP focuses on the position of 'Others' within or outwith European heritages and identities, attending particularly to the place and perception of Islam and to legacies of colonialism in contemporary European societies.

WP3 Cultural forms and expressions of identity in Europe

Cultural forms and expressions of identity in Europe focuses on cultural traditions as significant factors that form local, regional, national and European identities and the ways in which cultural communities and policy makers develop cultural tradition, maintain intangible cultural heritage and ensure its sustainability for future generations. The WP engages particularly with language, tourism, music and festivals within heritage contexts.

WP4 Digital heritage dialogue[s]: the role of digitally-enabled conversations in constructing heritage identities in Europe

Digital heritage dialogue[s]: the role of digitally-enabled conversations in constructing heritage identities in Europe engages with digital design methodologies to investigate heritage conversations online and on-site (i.e. in a museum/heritage setting and beyond), and to craft opportunities for talk/dialogue within exhibition and heritage settings to develop intercultural dialogue. The WP explores the potential of existing and future digital technologies (e.g. web- and mobile-based, alongside experimental bespoke tools for use in museums and sites) to provide deeper understandings of European heritage alongside reflexive identities and inclusive senses of belonging.

WP5 Education, heritage and identities

Education, heritage and identities develops best practices in the production and transmission of European heritages and identities within two sectors that face challenges in an age of immigration and globalization, namely education and cultural heritage production. It explores how European identity is shaped through formal and informal learning situations

both in and outside the classroom with the purpose of enhancing school curricula and informal learning at heritage sites by integrating innovative technologies and including multicultural perspectives.

WP6 Food as Heritage

Food as Heritage focuses on food as a fundamental element of heritage, and a very important one in times of crisis as a means of exploring identities. By adding culinary traditions to other forms of heritage, WP6 establishes an innovative synergy and adds value to the project by bringing together the cultural construction and invention of traditions, social practices, commercial practice, tourism, public policies and marketing strategies. The WP proposes food heritage as a basis for inclusive actions toward European citizens as well as immigrants who have not received citizen status.

What is the Cohere Critical Archive (CCA)?

One of the innovative aspects of the the CoHERE project is the Critical Archive (CCA) which provides a dynamic digital repository and linking mechanism for content produced through or in relation to the CoHERE project. This content includes critical essays, articles, reports and literature reviews, films and audio recordings, data files, case studies and profiles of practice-based research. As well as providing a home and linking structure for this content, the CCA unfolds and evolves over time. This allows it to register changes in thinking, contradictions and tensions, emerging areas and debates, reflections on current affairs, provocations, conjectures and forecasts related to notions of European heritage.

Project outputs can be reached from the CCA, available at: <https://research.ncl.ac.uk/cohere/coherecriticalarchive/>.

Istanbul Bilgi University's role in CoHERE

Istanbul Bilgi University's European Institute is involved in two Work Packages.

Work Package 2 "The use of past in political discourse and the representation of Islam in European museums" is led by Professor Ayhan Kaya and researchers from Istanbul Bilgi University with Dr Chiara de Cesari from University of Amsterdam, and researchers from Newcastle University, in collaboration with Dr Wayne Modest from National Museum of World Cultures.

Work Package 5 "Education, heritage and identities" is led by Professor Troels Myrup Christensen and researchers from Aarhus University with Dr Lia Galani and researchers from University of Athens and researchers from Istanbul Bilgi University and researchers from the Latvian Academy of Culture.

In the upcoming sections, we will discuss up to date information on our findings from the WP2 and innovative aspects of WP5.

WP2 “The use of past in political discourse and the representation of Islam in European museums”: Research findings

WP2 investigates public/popular discourses and dominant understandings of a homogeneous ‘European heritage’ and the ways in which they are mobilized by specific political actors to advance their agendas and to exclude groups such as minorities from a stronger inclusion into European society. What notions of European heritage circulate broadly in the public sphere and in political discourse? How do the ‘politics of fear’ relate to such notions of European heritage and identity across and beyond Europe and the EU? How is the notion of a European heritage and memory used not only to include and connect Europeans but also to exclude some of them? We are interested in looking into the relationship between a European memory and heritage-making and circulating notions of ‘race’, ethnicity, religion and civilization as well as contemporary forms of discrimination grounded in the idea of incommensurable cultural and memory differences.

There were three reports that were produced by the European Institute team. All reports are available at the CoHERE Critical Archive (<http://cohere-ca.ncl.ac.uk/>).

The first reports titled “The rise of populist extremism in Europe: Theoretical Tools for Comparison” (Kaya, 2016) conducts a literature survey based on theoretical and empirical analysis to bear on the questions of cause and response: what factors are causing growing numbers of citizens to endorse populist parties of right or left? Drawing on the theoretical review of the current state of populism in Europe, this report elaborates on the features of contemporary populism, which has become very widespread in the last decade in a Europe hit by financial and refugee crises. There are various approaches to analyse typologies of populism in Europe as well as in the other parts of the world however, the most common approach explains the populist vote with socio-economic factors. This approach argues that populist sentiments come out as the symptoms of detrimental effects of modernization and globalization, which is more likely to imprison working class groups. It is often presumed that the affiliates of such populist parties are political protestors, single-issue voters, “losers of globalization”, or ethno-nationalists. However, the picture seems to be more complex. Populist party voters are dissatisfied with, and distrustful of mainstream elites, and most importantly they are hostile to immigration and rising ethnocultural and religious diversity. While these citizens feel economically insecure, their hostility springs mainly from their belief that immigrants and minority groups are threatening their national culture, social security, community and way of life. They are perceived by the followers of the populist parties as a security challenge threatening social, political, cultural and economic unity and homogeneity of their nation.

The main concern of these citizens is not only the ongoing immigration and the refugee crisis, they are also profoundly anxious about Muslim-origin people who are already settled mostly in western European countries. Anti-Muslim sentiment has become an important driver of support for populist extremists - a sentiment that is based on the perception that all Muslim-origin people are ethnically, culturally, religiously, politically and economically homogenous. This means that appealing only to concerns over immigration such as calling for immigration numbers to be reduced or border controls to be tightened, is not enough. Populist parties seem to

be investing in the worsening economic conditions, public attitudes to immigration, attitudes and prejudices towards Muslims and Islam, and public dissatisfaction with the response of mainstream elites to these issues. The views and ideas they espouse cannot be dismissed as those of a marginal minority. It seems that these parties are here to stay. Public concern over immigration and rising cultural and ethnic diversity, anxiety over the presence and compatibility of Muslims, and dissatisfaction with the performance of mainstream elites on these issues are unlikely to subside. This report argues that a populist political style has become very widespread in Europe, together with the rise of neo-liberal forms of governmentality, capitalizing on what is presented as legitimate in cultural, ethnic, religious and civilizational terms. The supremacy of cultural-religious discourse in the West is likely to frame many of the social, political, and economic conflicts within the range of societies’ religious differences. Many of the ills faced by migrants and their descendants, such as poverty, exclusion, unemployment, illiteracy, lack of political participation, and unwillingness to integrate, are attributed to their Islamic background, believed stereotypically to clash with Western secular norms and values.

The second report titled “The rise of populist extremism in Europe: Lost in Diversity and Unity” (Kaya 2017) reveals the social-economic drivers of the contemporary forms of populist movements in Europe. This report provides the theoretical tools to compare the rise of populist movements in five EU countries (Germany, France, Greece, Italy, the Netherlands) as well as in Turkey. Kaya argues that the supporters of political parties and movements in Europe are feeling economically insecure, their hostility springs mainly from their belief that immigrants and minority groups are threatening their national culture, social security, community and way of life. Immigrants and minority groups are perceived by the populist party supporters as a security challenge threatening social, political, cultural and economic unity and homogeneity of their nation. The main concern of these citizens is not just the ongoing immigration and the refugee crisis; they are also concerned with already-settled Muslim communities in Europe. Anti-Muslim sentiment has become an important driver of support for populist extremists. This means that appealing only to concerns over immigration such as calling for immigration numbers to be reduced or border controls to be tightened, is not enough. The resentment against the symptoms of globalization seems to be one of the two essential drivers of populism leading to the feelings of getting lost in diversity among the followers of such political parties.

A second constituent of the contemporary forms of populist rhetoric is the growing resentment against the European Union, which is perceived by the affiliates of populism as one of the sources of the current political and economic crisis. The transnational character of the European Union has recently become one of the main focal points of criticism for the populist political leaders, who happen to invest in the capitalization of the feelings of getting lost in unity. It was also argued that populist political style has become very widespread together with the rise of neoliberal forms of governmentality capitalizing on what is cultural, ethnic, religious and civilizational. The supremacy of cultural-religious discourse in the West is likely to frame many of the social, political, and economic conflicts within the range of societies’ religious differences. Many of the ills faced by migrants and their descendants, such as poverty, exclusion, unemployment, illiteracy, lack of political participation, and unwillingness to integrate, are attributed to their Islamic background, believed stereotypically to clash with Western secular norms and values. Accordingly, this report argues that ‘Islamophobia’, rather than an inherent fear of Islam; ‘Islamophobia’ is a key ideological form in which social

and political contradictions of the neoliberal age are dealt with, and that this form of culturalization is embedded in migration-related inequalities as well as geopolitical orders. Culturalization of political, social, and economic conflicts has become a popular sport in a way that reduces all sorts of structural problems to cultural and religious factors – a simple way of knowing what is going on in the World for the individuals appealed to by populist rhetoric.

The third report titled “Islam versus Europe: Populist discourse and the construction of a civilizational identity” (Kaya and Tecmen 2018) reveals the ways in which five populist parties in Europe (Alternative for Germany in Germany, National Front in France, Party for Freedom in the Netherlands, Five Star Movement in Italy, and Golden Dawn in Greece, employ the fear of Islam as a political instrument to mobilize their supporters and to mainstream themselves. In order to do so, this report provides a discourse analysis of the manifestos of these populist parties, and the speeches of the key figures as well as referencing the individual interviews conducted in the scope of CoHERE. The report illustrates that the growing affiliation of the supporters of right-wing populist parties with culture, nativism, authenticity, ethnicity, religiosity, traditions, myths, and civilizational rhetoric provides them with an opportunity to establish solidarity networks against structural problems. The interviews show that the majority of the supporters of right-wing populist parties are not religious by habitus, they are mostly secular, agnostic, or even atheist. Such individuals who are on the one hand, socially, economically and politically deprived, and on the other hand, are in quest for communities to defend themselves against the detrimental effects of globalization are more likely to be appealed by right-wing populist discourses that simplify, binarize, culturalize, civilizationalize and religionize what is social, economic and political in origin. Right-wing populist party leaderships across Europe seem to be strongly capitalizing on civilizational matters by singling out Islam.

Discourse analysis of the speeches and manifestos of the right-wing populist parties in five countries also illustrates that these parties take on a civilizational approach to formulating Islam and the Christian West as intrinsic opposites. In parallel with the Huntingtonian paradigm of “Clash of Civilizations”, the term civilization here is reduced to religious differences, and Christianity as a cultural form, but not religious form, to be celebrated by liberals, atheists, agnostics, and others versus the rise of radical Islam challenging the secular forms of life. The feelings of social-economic and political deprivation are not only expressed by means of resentment against multiculturalism, diversity, migration and Islam, but also by means of resentment against the European Union institutions, which are believed to be imposing a unified transnational identity challenging national sovereignty and nativism.

Nation Branding and Culture: commercialising heritage

As we noted in the first part, Ayşe Tecmen published a Working Paper titled: “The Relations between public diplomacy and nation brands: an investigation of nation branding in Turkey” (Istanbul Bilgi University European Institute, Working Paper No: 10, May 2018). This paper is also published in the scope of the CoHERE project to discuss the relations between

states’ utilization of national culture and heritage assets to communicate with foreign publics.

In the last two decades, nation branding has become a discursive asset in politics due to the increasing significance of public opinion in countries’ ability to compete in a globalised economic and political setting. Due to the multiplicity of incentives to brand nations, this subject matter has received extensive attention from both academics and practitioners. This paper delineates the extant theoretical and academic debates on the relations between public diplomacy and nation brands, and sheds light on how nation brands are deployed to influence foreign public opinions. It also discusses the stages of nation branding which illustrates the complexity of the nation branding process while drawing attention to the importance of economic, political, and cultural assets. To illustrate how nation branding is used in practice, this paper focuses on the making of Brand Turkey as well as the recent projects and campaigns carried out in this scope. It reveals that there are both economic and political incentives to brand Turkey, and the diversity of the campaign carried out by the government illustrates their significance to formulating a unique, articulate, and competitive nation brand. This paper demonstrates that innovative approaches to diplomacy, particularly in terms of state-to-public communications, have become essential to ascertaining countries’ distinctive characteristics derived from their national assets.

Interview with Ayşe Tecmen, by Ekin Doruk (Intern at the European Institute)

This paper was in part presented at a CoHERE project conference in Athens, Greece in March 2017. The published version was discussed with BİLGİ students in May 2018 Spring Sessions. The following questions were compiled by our intern Ekin Doruk based on the commonly asked questions after Ayşe Tecmen’s presentations on nation branding.

What is nation branding and why is it significant in today’s world?

Nation branding is one those topics that we hear about in terms of economic policies and mostly in terms of tourism. This is especially the case in Turkey because branding has become sort of a hot topic. It’s actually a very interesting topic which we often discuss as an outcome of globalization. The main idea is the globalization has brought on such a deep level of integration that countries need to “market” themselves in a competitive way. Regional integration that we see in the case of the European Union is an excellent illustration of globalization’s outcomes.

So, nation branding is a way that countries market their differences in a way that helps them attract tourists, foreign investments, and increase exports. In effect, it is a commercially-driven process but since it concerns countries, or rather “nations”, it builds on national assets. These national assets are communicated to target audiences through six dimensions. These are tourism, exports, people of the branded nation, culture and heritage, governance which refers to both domestic and foreign policy, and foreign investment and immigration. It is rare that a country uses all six dimensions in a balanced fashion. Usually countries begin with tourism branding because this dimension usually receives funding from both state and non-state actors. Then, relevant actors identify national assets in different dimensions and devise their strategy after identifying the most salient dimensions.

Nation brands are very important in today's world because of increased economic and political competition which stems from globalization. Countries take control over their image and reputation by conducting branding activities. I should also note that it is not always a welcomed way of outward-image projection. Mostly, there is a philosophical objection to nation branding because we associate brands and branding with commercial brands. When we hear about a branding we think about Nike or Apple or Nokia, we don't think about Brand Spain or Brand Poland. There is a tendency to reject nation branding because people do not appreciate the association of the concept of a nation with a commercial process. This is because nation branding is misunderstood as the branding, or marketing, of national identity, which is an emotional and intimate concept.

Is there a Brand EU?

The EU does not have a distinct nation brand per se, but it has a competitive identity, which includes among others its flag, its slogan. As the EU itself is not a nation, its brand is much more complicated. However, EU member states have their own brands which were formulated around diverse national assets. Often, we see that newly-established brands in EU member states use their brands to promote their place within Europe by emphasizing their modern and European “face”. Perhaps the best examples are Spain and Poland, which both used nation branding, or rather outward image projection efforts, to get their European credentials.

An important thing about EU nation brands is the level of competition. When we think about the EU, we think about solidarity, and unity but surely these countries compete to attract tourists and investments. Think about Mediterranean countries, Mediterranean tourism is relatively standardized. It's about the sun, the sea and the sand. If you are seeking such a destination you have to decide between Spain, Italy, Croatia, and Greece. What makes one choose to visit Spain over Italy? Well, this is where culture and heritage are critical. Often when travelling individuals seek something new, and something different. So, culture becomes a key national asset in creating a distinct brand identity. Countries use this dimension extensively not to move away from their Europeanness or to reject European identity but to show that they have that “unique” element that makes them different and more alluring than other EU countries. In terms of branding, promotion of difference is not dangerous but rather practical.

I'm usually asked if this competition is detrimental to Europe or the EU. It's a difficult question. European culture and European identity are very complex, and they transform through enlargements. What remains more or less constant is the values that are generally associated with European culture and identity. For instance, the EU is associated with

modernity, secularism, democracy and the protection of human rights. In a way, EU membership endorses that country as having these values. This also stems from the idea that the EU is, for the lack of a better word, an embodiment of European values. Therefore, member states do not have to emphasize these values when reaching out to target audiences, instead they focus on unique elements of their culture. In other words, nation brands are not motivated by nationalism but rather by commercialism.

What would be Turkey's role is there was a Brand EU?

Well while there is no nation brand for the EU, it definitely has a distinct competitive identity. Identity in this sense is more than just the visual and verbal cues we associate with the Union. Its mostly about the values I talked about. As you know, Europe is experiencing economic, social, and identity crisis and there are different scenarios on the EUs future. These decrease trust in the Union's ability to maintain its objective of regional peace. The integrity of its external image is also being called into question. BREXIT, for instance, was detrimental to EU's image because it shattered the idea that member states' commitments to the Union were permanent. It also created an image of instability, which is also very damaging to its image.

It is likely that the EU will evolve into a brand in a strict sense. But its image and reputation could definitely benefit from Turkey's membership. At the very least, the Union's emphasis on diversity, tolerance and plurality could be illustrated by the inclusion of a seemingly “different” country. This could be a way of showing that the presence of populist parties and the discourse of a homogeneous identity did not affect the EU's approach towards Turkey. But I must also say that Turkey also needs to reaffirm its commitment to Europeanisation. Recently, we have been hearing about Brand Turkey, which is mainly focused on increasing the visibility of Turkish exports and increasing tourism revenue. Governance dimension is rarely addressed. This refers to the stability of both domestic and foreign relations and the soundness of these policies. Relations with the EU are extremely important to Brand Turkey and membership could indeed reaffirm Turkey's position within European, as well as the EU's commitment to diversity.

Special Topic:

The following is a literature review of the Ottoman “millet system” written by our Administrative Assistant Didem Balatlıoğulları who is also an MA student at the Cultural Management Programme at Istanbul Bilgi University. She is currently writing her MA thesis on being the “other” in Turkish cultural policies focusing specifically on the early-Republican period and the influences of Turkification policies.

Cultural Identities of the Minorities in the Ottoman Period: The “millet” system

Didem Balatlıoğulları, Istanbul Bilgi University's European Institute, Administrative Assistant and MA student in Cultural Management at Istanbul Bilgi University.

For centuries, Ottoman lands have been home to communities of different religions and ethno-cultures. One of the most important reasons of this multi-ethnic structure in the Ottoman Empire is the expansion policy, which was implemented especially in the 13th and 14th centuries (Adaklı, 2013). The Ottomans classified various ethnic groups living in their lands by anticipating the necessity to “protect cultural plurality in order to ensure political-administrative unity” in the Empire (Belge, 2008: 262).

In the 18th century, the relationship between the state and non-Muslim communities is the basis of the transition to

the nation system (Ahmad, 2014). The rules of Islam, which shaped the political and social structure of the Ottoman Empire are the most important factor in the structuring of the nation system according to religion (Ercüment, 2012). This was because Islam was ordering that those who accepted to live under the patronage of Muslims would be protected without any discrimination of language, religion and race (Özcoşar, 2003). Therefore, arrangements were made to enable them to live safely under Ottoman patronage without trying to change their religious and cultural characteristics. There were some important cultural rights granted to non-Muslim in the scope of this arrangement. For example, non-Muslims built a life staying true to their own culture and traditions. They were able to choose to reside in houses close to each other and were able to continue the traditions they were accustomed to. Most importantly, in order to govern themselves these communities had a religious leader, and these leaders managed their own internal affairs. In other words, the internal affairs of the non-Muslims, who had their own autonomous structure, were carried out through these leaders who are also served as bridges with the Empire. This structure helped maintain order in the society by creating a hierarchy between the palace and the non-Muslim minority. In this way, the intangible cultural heritage, values and traditions of these communities survived until this day. The Ottomans adopted these practices against the non-Muslim citizens, and also adopted the system of nations which aimed to maintain social peace and the coexistence of religious and cultural differences (Ahmad, 2014). Non-Muslims were able to use their own language in their own schools. The preservation of language has been the most important factor in the transfer of culture over generations.

The Effects of Constructing National Identity on the Minorities during Early Republican Period

The search for equality and freedom, which had spread all over the world following the French Revolution, led to divisions within the Ottoman society and the breakdown of the Ottoman patronage. In the following period, the political and military conflicts caused the Ottoman Empire to weaken gradually. The flow of nationalism in Europe began to spread and caused various problems in the Ottoman Empire as well (Gencer, 2009). In the face of these problems, in 1839, the Tanzimat Edict was declared. “Everyone under the rule of the Ottoman Empire, regardless of the religion and sect, is Ottoman” was declared in the Articles 8, 9, 10 and 11 of the decree (Adaklı, 2013). This decree was implemented as an emergency plan to prevent social disintegration (Gencer, 2009). Following this process, the Reform Edict was declared in 1856 and with this decree non-Muslims gained some freedoms. In the 19th century, the equality status provided to non-Muslims constructed a new middle-class with ethnic and religious consciousness by modernizing non-Muslim communities much faster than the Muslims through the economic and educational support of the West (Güngör, 2017).

The First World War and the Constitutional Monarchy period reshaped every social matter in the Ottoman Empire and the main issue was identity politics (Ahmad, 2014). During the Constitutional Period, the problem of identity intensified, and individuals began to define themselves as Turkish instead of Ottomans (Ahmad, 2014). This changed the identity discourses. This experience in the last period of the Ottoman Empire, was influential in the definition of Turkish identity. The search for a new identity, which was especially favored by the intelligentsia began to spread rapidly among the society. After 1908, Turkification became more institutionalized (Gencer, 2009). Especially the works of Ziya Gökalp formed the foundations of Turkishness and Turkification policies (Bars, 2017). Following this period, Ottoman identity was replaced by Turkish identity, and a great transformation

began in the Empire. This transformation was completed with the establishment of the Republic of Turkey.

One of the most prominent characteristics of the single-party period, namely the Republican People's Party government, was the policy of Turkification of minorities following a top-down approach to identity politics. The second policy was the policy of Turkification of the economy. Through exercise of political power, non-Muslim citizens' economic sovereignty was transferred to Turkish-Muslims who were considered to be “the real owners of the country”. This entailed various practices such as the Wealth Tax Act which provided minorities with a minimum level of economic activity in the social sphere” (Bali, 2009: 44). In order to remove non-Muslims from commercial life, the Wealth Tax imposed an obligation to pay high taxes that most non-Muslims were not able to cover. Those who could not pay their taxes were sent to labor camps under severe conditions and their property was confiscated (Aydın, 2018).

Non-Muslims, who were able to maintain their own culture and traditions under the millet system in the Ottoman period, faced severe problems in the process of creating a new nation. These problems covered everything from non-Muslims' daily lives to their culture, from their jobs to schools. In the single-party period, the policies implemented as a result of the government's efforts to rapidly Turkify non-Muslims created a cultural pressure on the latter. With the Turkification of the education system, use of languages other than Turkish were prohibited in non-Muslim schools. In addition, non-Muslims' names were replaced with Turkish names (Bali, 2005). For instance, the “Citizen, Speak Turkish” campaign instituted an intense pressure to abandon non-Turkish languages.

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WP 5 Education, heritage and identities

Education, heritage and identities develops best practices in the production and transmission of European heritages and identities within two sectors that face challenges in an age of immigration and globalization, namely education and cultural heritage production. It explores how European identity is shaped through formal and informal learning situations both in and outside the classroom with the purpose of enhancing school curricula and informal learning at heritage sites by integrating innovative technologies and including multicultural perspectives.

WP5 is led by Professor Troels Myrup Christensen and researchers from Aarhus University with Dr Lia Galani and researchers from University of Athens, and researchers from Istanbul Bilgi University, and researchers from the Latvian Academy of Culture.

Digital Textbook: “Education, Heritage and Europe: Understanding Europe’s Current Predicaments”

One of the digital outputs from WP5 is the e-book titled: “Education, Heritage and Europe: Understanding Europe’s Current Predicaments”, which was managed by Istanbul Bilgi University’s European Institute. This is digital textbook that is prepared by the WP5 team for teaching secondary school students on the current identity, refugee, and financial crisis in Europe. The textbook includes the following chapters:

- **Introduction:** “Do you feel European?” (Christopher Whitehead)
- **Chapter 1:** Space and Identity: Mapping Europe in an Age of Crisis (Troels Myrup Kristensen)
- **Chapter 2:** Europe and European Union in Geographic Education Curricula: a case study (Lia Galani)
- **Chapter 3:** European Economic Integration and the Debt Crisis (Ayşe Tecmen)
- **Chapter 4:** Europe, Migration and the Refugee Crisis (Ayhan Kaya and Ayşe Tecmen)
- **Chapter 5:** Europe on Display: a Case Study (Susannah Eckersley)

The e-book and all its components are available at the CoHERE Critical Archive (<http://cohere-ca.ncl.ac.uk/>).

Animated Cartoon on “Populism, diversity and tolerance”

The textbook also includes a short animation titled “Populism, diversity and tolerance” sketched by Emrah Ablak, to discuss European identity and the significance of tolerance in a multicultural Europe.

Digital Game “Europe in a Museum”

The e-book also includes a digital game titled “Europe in a Museum”, which can be accessed from the e-book as well as separately through <http://criticalheritage.bilgi.edu.tr>. The game was supervised by Nuri Kara (Istanbul Bilgi University, Digital Game Design Department).

The graphics of the game were prepared by Egecan Kömür, and Gina Al Halabi, who are undergraduate students at Istanbul Bilgi University.

Digital games have become central to both formal and informal education. With that in mind, we explored the suitable ways of designing a game on heritage to illustrate that while tangible and intangible heritage are considered separate categories, the distinction is not rigid. In selecting and collecting the different heritage assets for EU countries, we frequently explored the UNESCO website. As the game will illustrate, heritage is a comprehensive term that encompasses music, dance, crafts, literature, arts, architecture, festivals, re-enactments as well as other significant elements of national and European memory. Sometimes these elements are shared by various European

countries, thus becoming a part of their shared memory. In some of cases, certain elements can be a part of European collective memory, which transcends national boundaries thereby becoming a component of European heritage and identity.

Teacher’s Guide

The teacher’s guide is an adaptable resource to support students and teachers as they explore and engage with the e-book during their lessons. The lessons were devised to provide an interactive learning environment which includes multiple digital sources produced outside the CoHERE project. These include videos, visuals, online quizzes, as well as links to a virtual museum to facilitate discussion on Europeanness, the notion of heritage, as well as the relations between national and European identities. In doing so, the teacher’s guide is intended as an innovative intervention which is designed to illustrate the significance of digital outputs in interactive learning.

Digital Games and Heritage Education

The following short essays were prepared to highlight the growing interest in digital games in education and the influence of digital technologies on heritage education. The first piece is written by Nuri Kara (Istanbul Bilgi University, Head of the Digital Game Design Department) who supervised the design of the digital game “Europe in a Museum”. The second piece is written by Lia Galani (National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Department of Sciences of Education) who is a principal investigator in the CoHERE project.

Digital Gaming in Education

Nuri Kara, Ph.D, İstanbul Bilgi University, Head of the Digital Game Design Department and Designer of the Interactive E-book’s Digital Game for CoHERE Work Package 5

Thanks to the digital distribution channels and the continuing introduction of new platforms, digital gaming has become a highly competitive and truly global industry within the last decade. Education has been one of the leading fields in that global industry because several gaming applications have been created for it. Since new generation has a strong contact to digital gaming, integrating its components into curricular or extra-curricular activities can support teaching and learning. It can also be seen as an alternative medium helping teach specific skills in an enjoyable manner.

Gamification is a term used for gamifying several topics from a variety of fields, such as education, commerce, medicine and so on. Gamification in education has several applications for different disciplines, such as math, physics and history. For instance, a city can be created in a game world, and a boy who uses skateboard tries to solve the mathematical puzzles to accomplish the game related mission in that city. This can be an example for supporting to teach simple calculations for primary school students. As another example, player tries to win the race without collecting the items giving damage

to the global climate. This can be an example for increasing the awareness of adults toward global warming. It can be understood from these examples that gamification can be applied for both children and adults in order to support teaching specific skills in a practical way.

Toys play an important role in children’s lives and there are ways to integrate gaming applications into toys for purposeful and meaningful tasks. In my study, I developed a smart toy including radio frequency identification (RFID) reader and tags inserted into plush toys. These plush toys interact with the computer-based animation with RFID tags. Children can put any plush toy onto the RFID reader and see the virtual image of that toy on the screen. The main aim of this smart toy is to do specific tasks or make storytelling. For instance, children provided different stories based on the selection of specific toys and their virtual actions on the screen. In addition, children tried to put the correct toy to complete the pattern in a correct way. That is, the main goal of using smart toy is to improve children’s several skills such as social life skills and simple logical skills by combining gaming components with physical toys.

With the popularity of mobile phones and tablets, it is easy to reach several digital gaming applications. Besides, new gaming technologies, such as artificial intelligence, virtual reality and augmented reality have become popular. Artificial intelligence aims to create machines acting and working like humans. Virtual reality is a three-dimensional, computer-generated environment. People directly interact with that environment for exploring purposes. Augmented reality combines virtual life elements with real life components. It is possible to see more applications of these new technologies in the field of education very soon.

Although new technologies have been common today’s world day by day, we should be careful while integrating them into education. Technology cannot solve all educational problems. It is important to see that technology is a tool for supporting teaching and learning activities. It cannot be seen as a goal for reaching the desired outcomes. Digital gaming has several positive effects on students. Since they are very active in today’s gaming world and online gaming tournaments, we should be aware of the potential of digital gaming for educational purposes. For creating the effective gaming applications, it is important to create teams including game designers, academicians, psychologists and subject matter experts. Hence, new projects should be written to design and develop games for educational areas focusing on improving specific skills. Students’ reactions and feedbacks should also be received to understand the usability and effectiveness of the games. The most important thing is to design and develop digital games, which are suitable to students’ needs and expectations.

Reinforcing Heritage dialogue through «Eurocraft» serious game prototype

Lia Galani, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Assistant Professor at the Department of Sciences of Education, and Principal Investigator for CoHERE at National and Kapodistrian University of Athens

The use of virtual or digital applications in the field of cultural heritage (museums, historical/ archaeological sites, etc.), is a trend which aims to make the cultural content more accessible to the broad public by helping visitors to learn through their engagement in digital experiences. However, these applications most often fall to the “storytelling narratives” category rather than to that of interactive applications. Nowadays, the findings that Europeans do not know much about their own cultural heritage or the cultural heritage of other Europeans (Pöllmann, 2007; Philippou, 2007; Faas, 2011b; Karatza, Galani & Halkia, 2018), triggered a discussion concerning the presentation and popularization of cultural heritage through serious games. The main idea behind serious games design is to use their positive influence in learning. In addition, they help individuals to

achieve the educational objectives and content delivery through a pleasant experience (Bellotti et al. 2012; Connolly et al. 2012; Mortara, et al. 2014; Malegiannaki & Daragoumis, 2017; Troyer, 2017).

“Eurocraft” serious game prototype first screen

Educators are well aware that engaging people in creating content help them to gain more stable knowledge which is very important in the field of heritage. Moreover, from a pedagogical perspective, playing games has proven benefits regarding cognitive skills (read, write, think, analyze, understand, remember, enhance attention, solve problems, etc.), motivational skills (learning by doing, learning by failure, assigning tasks, feedback, etc.), emotional skills (mood - emotion manage, empathy, awareness, safety, positive attitude, etc.). These benefits, together with interactivity and high social penetration, make games a powerful tool. Considering that pupils learn best, and enjoy most, when working on personally meaningful projects, the research team of National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (Department of Primary Education) developed in the framework of WP5 CoHERE project (Horizon 2020), a serious game prototype under the title “Eurocraft – Exploring critical heritages through vid-maps”.

The game is aimed to students 12-17-year-olds with a view [i] to promote the communication of cultural heritage(s) between young people within Europe, [ii] to encourage the dialogue for the notion of “Sense of place” as well as of the “European Other”, [iii] to help students understand Europe’s multicultural physiognomy and [iv] to encourage them to talk about their cultural experiences.

The game “Eurocraft” is built on a scenario that may be real: The aircraft “Eurocraft” travels around Europe as a matrix to collect data (images, videos, sound) and stories concerning European Heritage and Identity. The material uploaded by the players (“footprints”), their participation in games as well as the creation of multilayer dot maps are the keys to unlock the stands with the heritage objects and create a three-floor heritage air-museum.

The collection of semantic data on heritage “footprints” created by players, will be used by researchers to help uncover new insights about [i] the perceptual regions of pupils from different parts of Europe, [ii] the perceptual regions of pupils from different countries of the world who live in Europe (immigrants) or have been born in Europe by immigrant parents, and [iii] the role of a virtual map collection in the building of the European identity. By the term perceptual region, we refer to a construct that reflects human attitudes and feelings about places and thus is defined by people’s shared personal understanding of those places. Perceptual regions serve to reflect the aspects of people’s mental maps and although they may help to prescribe a personal sense of structure on the world, they often do so on the basis of a stereotype. The area of perceptual regions is an unexplored area in typical education (because of the structure of education itself) and that is why it seems a very interesting area in the field of geography education.

“Eurocraft” serious game prototype-Europe (avatar) welcome Euronauts (players) to the game.

In order to design the game, we set a high priority on its pedagogical structure, the task typologies, as well as on game’s design:

Pedagogical structure: The game has been grounded on different pedagogical theories for formal and non-formal education context. It relies on a generalization of game-based learning theory (use of games for teaching a subject matter, challenging students to learn through a highly motivated learning experience) as well as of task-based learning theory (use of specific activities through which students are free to use any language they want, to share information or experiences, to play games, etc.). It also supports challenges, learning by doing, guided discovery and collaboration. The environment of the game is friendly and the use of a virtual character, named Europe, facilitates players (Euronauts) by making them feel welcome and safe to express themselves and share their thoughts and ideas concerning heritage. The game rewards players by letting them built their own cultural museum when all tasks have been completed. The use of rewards is carefully selected as a medium to increase motivation.

Task typologies: The game tries to communicate heritage by using channels of communication familiar to teenagers. The philosophy of tasks lies in the area of social media and crowdsourcing platforms and the way people communicate through them (i.e. how do they upload and share stories and moments in Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, the use of hashtags, etc.)

All tasks are performed through specific rooms of the Eurocraft. For example, in the Observatory, users work in an interactive vid-map environment. They communicate their cultural heritage footprint to the other Euronauts by uploading representations and performances connected to ideas of place, history, tradition and belonging (Vid-maps >Upload footprint), they use hashtags to categorise the information they upload, they comment on footprints of other Euronauts (Vid-maps>Comment footprint), they evaluate how well the cultural heritage of other Euronauts is presented in their footprints (Vid-maps>Rate footprint) or they create their own cultural heritage map based on different criteria (Vid-maps>Create a dot map). The other rooms of the Eurocraft are connected to games.

Users create by themselves a database of games ready to be played by the other users, they investigate more about European heritage by playing games which have been uploaded by other users, or they pass the challenge of the ten random questions of Eurometer in order to measure their feeling of being Europeans as well as their knowledge about EU.

Design criteria: Eurocraft, is designed as a web application to be played on portable devices or desktops. Two of the main design criteria taken in account was the diversity of supported types of tasks (stories, games, maps) so people with widely varying interests will be all able to work on topics they care about and the personalization (ability for people to import photos and music clips, writing texts etc.)

One of the rooms of “Eurocraft” aircraft, the “Observatory”. In this room Euronauts can upload footprints, rate and comment on the other players’ footprints and create multilayer dot maps

The application has already been tested by a small sample of pupils, preservice teachers and educators in order to prove all aspects of the architectural, pedagogical and cognitive concept. It is now on the phase of the beta edition which means in a stage of the ongoing testing process and in the following months it is planned to be tested in multicultural schools.

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